

FINAL DISSEMINATION REPORT

D6.7

TRANSFORM

Deliverable description

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D6.7 Final dissemination report

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AEIDL

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PU: Public (must be available on the website)

CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CI: Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Statement of originality

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Summary.

Regional research and innovation plans are key drivers for local regional development. By adopting RRI approaches to their R&I policies and actions, TRANSFORM aims to achieve more open, transparent and democratic R&I ecosystems within three regional clusters (Lombardy, Catalonia and Brussels-Capital), leading towards more responsible territorial development. The implementing regional clusters have designed, tested and disseminated three methodological frameworks (participatory research agenda setting, multi-stakeholder engagement and citizen science) at the forefront of the planning and implementation of their S3 strategies.

Through WP6 Sharing results and maximizing impact, TRANSFORM aims to improve overall general awareness about RRI, create a dialogue between institutions dedicated to territorial development through wide dissemination of project results, dedicated to empowering diverse stakeholders to implement and/or engage with the development of RRI, promote shared learning and governance innovations. WP6 worked closely with other WPs to ensure two-way communication flows and sharing of information to maximise the impact of the project.

The TRANSFORM Communication and Dissemination Plan was a living document, initially submitted in M4 and updated in M15. D6.7 Final dissemination report provides an overview of communication and dissemination activities that took place throughout the implementation of the project, and evaluation against the set KPIs.

In the following sections, the key features are presented in detail:

- Communication objectives
- Stakeholder mapping
- Communication channels and tools
- Communication and dissemination products
- Quality Control, Monitoring and Reporting

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TRANSFORM communication objectives

The core mission of TRANSFORM was to become an inspiring model of effective integration of RRI in territorial development, transferable to other regions.

Project objectives (POs)

- **PO1:** ESTABLISH a more open, transparent and democratic R&I ecosystems within three regional clusters (Lombardy, Catalonia and Brussels-Capital);
- **PO2:** CONSOLIDATE Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation (RIS3) by integrating an RRI approach within existing regional innovation processes;
- **PO3:** EMPOWER diverse stakeholders to implement and/or engage with the development of responsible regional development processes and evaluate their impact;
- **PO4:** EXPLORE concrete R&I working methods based on three sound methodological approaches: participatory research agenda setting, citizen science and design for social innovation;
- **PO5:** ADVANCE territorial Responsible Research and Innovation by promoting shared learning and diffusion of governance innovations.

Communication objectives (COs) and key messages (KMs)

The Communication and Dissemination Plan played a key role in supporting the project in achieving its objectives. In this respect, the Plan set forth the following communication objectives:

- **CO1:** to increase the visibility of the project and its activities,
- **CO2:** to showcase how our project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, so as to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices;
- **CO3:** to engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities and outcomes and multi-stakeholder involvement;
- **CO4:** to raise awareness about RRI and citizen engagement/participatory approaches within regional R&I decision making and their use and benefits;
- **CO5:** to build synergies with other EU-funded projects, networks and initiatives on RRI in territorial development, foster collaboration, avoid duplication and maximise impact;
- **CO6:** to widely disseminate TRANSFORM results beyond the regional government involved in the consortium and project community, ensuring they are available for the further uptake, also after the completion of TRANSFORM.

TRANSFORM's key messages were adapted to each target audience, as explained below:

- **KM1:** Citizen engagement and participatory approaches contribute to openness, inclusiveness and transparency in the regional R&I systems.
- **KM2:** RRI better aligns R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society.
- **KM3:** Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (civil society, research and university, industry and public administration).
- **KM4:** Participatory processes in the regional R&I ecosystem represent an opportunity to actively involve civil society (including citizens, CSOs and NGOs) in decision-making; moving from being a passive receiver to an active participant.
- **KM5:** Citizen engagement as new form of governance represents an opportunity for multiple perspectives and creativity in designing innovative solutions with a concrete territorial impact, contributing to tackling current challenges faced by society
- **KM6:** Concrete examples of responsible territorial development and tested approaches inspire and support regional authorities in transforming regional R&I ecosystems towards RRI.

Stakeholder mapping

Good communication is about giving the right information to the right audience at the right time and in the right format. Mapping all the relevant stakeholders and their interest is of capital importance to achieving the project's objectives. The stakeholder mapping links target audiences with the communications objectives, as well as activities that will facilitate engagement. This detailed mapping allowed for planning and design of targeted communication for each segment of the target audience from the onset of the project, and iteratively co-develop key messages. Based on this approach, the communications and dissemination activities were delivered to aim for maximum impact. TRANSFORM identified 6 specific target groups for communications activities illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: TRANSFORM target groups

The following table presents the stakeholder mapping for TRANSFORM and the communications objectives related to each of them. For each category, key messages, channels and goals are detailed in the table below (Table 1).

Table 1: Targeted communication per audience

Target audience (WHO?)	Communication objectives (CO) (WHAT?)	Communication Key messages (KM) (WHAT?)	Outreach channels (WHERE?)
Citizens and CSOs, NGOs	<p>CO1: to increase the visibility of the project and its activities,</p> <p>CO2: to showcase how our project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices;</p> <p>CO3: to engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities and outcomes and multi-stakeholder involvement;</p> <p>CO4: to raise awareness about RRI and citizen engagement/participatory approaches within regional R&I decision making and their use and benefits;</p>	<p>KM2: RRI better aligns R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society.</p> <p>KM3: Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (citizens, private sector, research and education, third-sector organisations).</p> <p>KM5: Co-creation and participatory approaches as new forms of governance represent an opportunity for multiple perspectives and creativity in designing innovative solutions with a concrete territorial impact, contributing to tackling current challenges faced by the society.</p>	<p>Project e-book; Social Media; Website; Dedicated public events; Partners channels; Videos; Promo materials; Local capacity building activities (WP2); Final local events.</p>
Public authorities (at all levels)	<p>CO1: to increase the visibility of the project and its activities,</p> <p>CO2: to showcase how our project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices;</p> <p>CO3: to engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities and outcomes and multi-stakeholder involvement;</p> <p>CO4: to raise awareness about RRI and citizen engagement/participatory approaches within regional R&I decision making and their use and benefits;</p> <p>CO5: to build synergies with other EU-funded projects, networks and initiatives on RRI in territorial development, foster collaboration, avoid duplication and maximise impact;</p> <p>CO6: to widely disseminate TRANSFORM results beyond the regional government involved in the consortium and project community, ensuring they are available for the further uptake, also after the completion of TRANSFORM.</p>	<p>KM1: Co-design and participatory approaches imply openness, inclusiveness and transparency in the regional R&I systems.</p> <p>KM2: RRI better aligns R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society.</p> <p>KM3: Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (citizens, private sector, research and education, third-sector organisations).</p> <p>KM4: Co-creation and participatory processes represent an opportunity to actively involve a wide range of stakeholders from civil society (including citizens, CSOs and NGOs) in decision-making; moving from being a passive receiver to an active participant.</p> <p>KM5: Co-creation and participatory approaches as new forms of governance represent an opportunity for multiple perspectives and creativity in designing innovative solutions with a concrete territorial impact, contributing to tackling current challenges faced by the society.</p>	<p>Project e-book; Social Media; Website; Final local events; Deliverables; Videos; Final conference; Partners' channels.</p>

		KM6: Concrete examples of responsible territorial development and tested approaches inspire and support regional authorities in transforming regional R&I ecosystems towards RRI.	
Academia & Research	<p>CO1: to increase the visibility of the project and its activities,</p> <p>CO2: to showcase how our project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices;</p> <p>CO3: to engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities and outcomes and multi-stakeholder involvement;</p> <p>CO4: to raise awareness about RRI and citizen engagement/participatory approaches within regional R&I decision making and their use and benefits;</p> <p>CO5: to build synergies with other EU-funded projects, networks and initiatives on RRI in territorial development, foster collaboration, avoid duplication and maximise impact;</p> <p>CO6: to widely disseminate TRANSFORM results beyond the regional government involved in the consortium and project community, ensuring they are available for the further uptake, also after the completion of TRANSFORM.</p>	<p>KM1: Co-design and participatory approaches imply openness, inclusiveness and transparency in the regional R&I systems.</p> <p>KM2: RRI better aligns R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society.</p> <p>KM3: Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (citizens, private sector, research and education, third-sector organisations).</p> <p>KM4: Co-creation and participatory processes represent an opportunity to actively involve a wide range of stakeholders from civil society (including citizens, CSOs and NGOs) in decision-making; moving from being a passive receiver to an active participant.</p> <p>KM5: Co-creation and participatory approaches as new forms of governance represent an opportunity for multiple perspectives and creativity in designing innovative solutions with a concrete territorial impact, contributing to tackling current challenges faced by the society.</p>	<p>Social Media;</p> <p>Website;</p> <p>Final local events;</p> <p>Final Conference;</p> <p>Project e-book;</p> <p>Deliverables;</p> <p>Partners' channels.</p>
Industry & companies	<p>CO1: to increase the visibility of the project and its activities,</p> <p>CO2: to showcase how our project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices;</p> <p>CO3: to engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities and outcomes and multi-stakeholder involvement;</p> <p>CO4: to raise awareness about RRI and citizen engagement/participatory approaches within regional R&I decision making and their use and benefits;</p>	<p>KM1: Co-design and participatory approaches imply openness, inclusiveness and transparency in the regional R&I systems.</p> <p>KM2: RRI better aligns R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society.</p> <p>KM3: Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (citizens, private sector, research and education, third-sector organisations).</p> <p>KM4: Co-creation and participatory processes represent an opportunity to actively involve a wide range of stakeholders from civil society (including citizens, CSOs and NGOs) in decision-making; moving from being a passive receiver to an active participant.</p>	<p>Social Media;</p> <p>Website;</p> <p>Final local events;</p> <p>Press releases;</p> <p>Project e-book;</p> <p>Deliverables;</p> <p>Videos;</p> <p>Partners channels;</p> <p>Final conference.</p>

<p>Media</p>	<p>CO1: to increase the visibility of the project and its activities, CO2: to showcase how our project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results and disseminate our good practices; CO3: to engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities and outcomes and multi-stakeholder involvement; CO4: to raise awareness about RRI and citizen engagement/participatory approaches within regional R&I decision making and their use and benefits;</p>	<p>KM1: Co-design and participatory approaches imply openness, inclusiveness and transparency in the regional R&I systems. KM2: RRI better aligns R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society. KM3: Regional policies, strategies and action plans should reflect the needs of all societal actors (citizens, private sector, research and education, third-sector organisations). KM4: Co-creation and participatory processes represent an opportunity to actively involve a wide range of stakeholders from civil society (including citizens, CSOs and NGOs) in decision-making; moving from being a passive receiver to an active participant. KM5: Co-creation and participatory approaches as new forms of governance represent an opportunity for multiple perspectives and creativity in designing innovative solutions with a concrete territorial impact, contributing to tackling current challenges faced by the society. KM6: Concrete examples of responsible territorial development and tested approaches inspire and support regional authorities in transforming regional R&I ecosystems towards RRI.</p>	<p>Social Media; Website; Press releases; Promo materials; Project events; Final conference.</p>
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Regional Think Tanks

To ensure active and multi-stakeholder participation, each regional cluster engaged relevant local stakeholders, representing the quadruple helix actors (universities, research groups, associations, CSOs, NGOs, science policy institutions, local businesses, professional associations, formal and informal educational institutions, science mediators) with the aim of contributing to mapping, reflecting and action development. Think Tank members contributed to the activities carried out within each cluster by providing a variety of views, know-how and priorities, therefore ensuring that all societal needs are taken into account in the implementation of innovative solutions to responsible territorial developments.

Multipliers

This Strategy aimed at achieving maximum impact with controlled spending by selecting channels that are the most effective in reaching out to the various target groups and **building upon multipliers**, namely consortium partners and relevant stakeholders at EU, national, regional and local level. Multipliers were invited to share the relevant activities, results and outcomes of the project using their own communications channels, and tools.

Within the project partnership, the multiplier effect was ensured by the involvement of consortium partners that have a strong and well-structured presence at regional level, with widespread and multi-stakeholder networks. Furthermore, the regional focus was reinforced by the involvement of regional Think Tank members.

At the European level, the multiplier effect focused on the involvement of organisations and professionals, dealing with the topics of TRANSFORM, that were well connected with EU institutions and networks, as well as well-established European-level channels with which project partners had a good track record of engagement and participation.

The **Advisory Board** members, representing acclaimed experts in their respective fields, also supported the dissemination of the results and maximise the visibility of the project.

TRANSFORM took advantage of existing channels of consortium partners. Partners were activating their channels and networks to maximise outreach, visibility of the project, and communication and dissemination efforts

Table 2 below provides an exhaustive list compiled by all partners that offer an overview of other channels/tools used to multiply the content and outcomes.

Table 2: Communication and dissemination partners of project partners

Organisation	Channels
FGB	Website Twitter: @FGBassetti Facebook: @fondazionebassetti + Private Group: Fondazione Giannino Bassetti LinkedIn: Fondazione Giannino Bassetti + Group: Fondazione Giannino Bassetti Instagram: fondazionebassetti & IGTV Vimeo: Fondazione Giannino Bassetti Flickr: fondazionebassetti YouTube: FondazioneBassetti Issuu: fondazionebassetti Slideshare: FondazioneBassetti Newsletter (monthly; English and Italian) Podcast: "I dialoghi di Fondazione Bassetti" https://anchor.fm/fondazione-giannino-bassetti (also in iTunes, Google Play and Spotify)
BEpart	Website Twitter: @BeParticipation Facebook: @BEparticipation YouTube: BEparticipation
SfC	Website Twitter: @SciencefChange LinkedIn: Science for Change
UiB	Website Twitter: @vitenskapsteori Facebook: @vitenskapsteorl
UB	Website Twitter: @OpenSystemsUB Vimeo: Open Systems Flickr: OpenSystems
UCLouvain	Website Twitter: @UCLouvain_be Facebook: @UCLouvain LinkedIn: Université catholique de Louvain YouTube: UCLouvain - Université catholique de Louvain
Finlombardia	Website LinkedIn: Finlombarda S.p.A. Newsletter (monthly; Italian) Lombardy Region collaborative platform Facebook: @OpenInnovationLombardia Twitter: @LombardiaInnova LinkedIn: Open Innovation Lombardia YouTube: Open Innovation Lombardia
RL	Website Twitter: @RegLombardia Facebook: @Regione.Lombardia.official LinkedIn: Regione Lombardia YouTube: Regione Lombardia
GENCAT	Website Twitter @gencat Facebook: @gencat

	Instagram: @gencat YouTube: gencat Newsletter
Innoviris	Website Twitter: @Innoviris Facebook: @innoviris LinkedIn: INNOVIRIS
AEIDL	Website Facebook: @AEIDL.asbl Twitter: @AEIDL LinkedIn: AEIDL eLibrary (repository) Flash newsletter (bi-monthly: English and French)
MoS	Website Twitter: @museumofscience Facebook: @museumofscience LinkedIn: Museum of Science Instagram: @museumofscience YouTube: BostonMOS

Related projects and initiatives

TRANSFORM continuously sought to build synergies with other relevant projects. Special attention is given to the EU-funded projects under the call II [SwafS-14-2018-2019-2020 - Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation](#), exploring potential synergies and cooperation in communication and dissemination activities, but also in other project activities such as evaluation and monitoring, to maximise impact and foster peer learning. TRANSFORM project partners took part in various activities to build these synergies, as illustrated in the table below.

In addition to projects, cooperation of the institutions and other initiatives were sought to explore synergies and opportunities for mutual visibility. An exhaustive list of projects, initiatives, and organisations and a description of specific activities is provided below.

Table 3: Relevant projects/initiatives TRANSFORM explored synergies

PROJECTS
WBC-RRI.NET: Embedding RRI in Western Balkan Countries: Enhancement of Self-Sustaining R&I Ecosystems (H2020-SwafS-2020-1)
RRI-LEADERS: Leveraging Leadership for Responsible Research and Innovation in Territories (H2020-SwafS-2020-1)
SeeRRI: Building Self-Sustaining Research and Innovation Ecosystems in Europe through Responsible Research and Innovation (H2020-SwafS-2018-1)
DigiTeRRI: Responsible Research and Innovation Approach for Transitioning the Traditional Industry Regions into Digitalised Industry Territories . (H2020-swafs-2019-1)
RRI2SCALE: Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy (H2020-SwafS-2019-1)

TeRRitoria: Territorial Responsible Research and Innovation Through the involvement of local R&I Actors (H2020-SwafS-2018-1)
TeRRIFICA: Territorial RRI fostering Innovative Climate Action (H2020-SwafS-2018-1)
SUPER MORRI (SwafS-21-2018)
MARIE Project (Interreg Europe)
INCENTIVE: Establishing Citizen Science Hubs in European Research Performing and Funding Organisations to drive institutional change and ground Responsible Research and Innovation in society (SwafS-23-2020 - Grounding RRI in society with a focus on citizen science)
NewHoRRizon: Excellence in science and innovation for Europe by adopting the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (SwafS-09-2016 - Moving from constraints to openings, from red lines to new frames in Horizon 2020)
GRACE (Grounding RRI Actions to Achieve Institutional Changes in European Research Funding and Performing Organisations) (SwafS-05-2018-2019 - Grounding RRI practices in research and innovation funding and performing organisations)
tetRRIS: Territorial Responsible Research and Innovation and Smart Specialisation (SwafS-14-2018-2019-2020 - Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation)
TeRRifica: Territorial RRI fostering Innovative Climate Action (SwafS-14-2018-1- Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation)
ENJOI: Engagement And Journalism Innovation For Outstanding Open Science Communication (SwafS-19-2018-2019-2020 - Taking stock and re-examining the role of science communication)
MOSAIC: Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation (H2020-SwafS-2018-2020 / H2020-SwafS-2020-1)
BRIDGES – Building Reflexivity and response-ability Involving Different narratives of knowledGES (Fondazione Cariplo)
FETA – Fair Energy Transition for All (King Baudouin Foundation)
Participatory initiatives for transforming and developing the Italian mountains in a sustainable way
CrAft (Creating Actionable Futures) (HORIZON-MISS-2021-CIT-01-02 - Collaborative local governance models to accelerate the emblematic transformation of urban environment and contribute to the New European Bauhaus initiative and the objectives of the European Green Deal)
NetZeroCities (LC-GD-1-2-2020 - Towards Climate-Neutral and Socially Innovative Cities)
CoR Bertelsmann Stiftung project
INITIATIVES & INSTITUTIONS
OECD – Open Government, Civic Space and Public Communication Unit
OECD - Committee for Scientific and Technological Policy (CSTP), Working Party on Bio-, Nano- and Converging Technologies (BNCT)
Community of Practice of the Competence Centre on Participatory and Deliberative Democracy
ERRIN – European Regions Research and Innovation Network
European Commission, Joint Research Centre (Ispra and Sevilla)
European Commission, DG REGIO
European Commission, DG RTD and REA
European Committee of the Regions
Bertelsmann Stiftung

TRANSFORM project partners pursued the following actions in order to build synergies:

M1-M15

- FGB took part in the [Ricerca, innovazione e bene comune webinar](#) organised by Art-ER (one of the implementing partners of [TeRRitoria project](#) with activities in Emilia-Romagna, Italy), which took place on 25 September 2020. TRANSFORM and the citizen engagement methodologies explored in the project were presented during the webinar, followed by open discussion. The event was held in Italian as it was devoted to Italian stakeholders only, with around 100 participants.
- A capacity building session: [The methodology of the RRI Maturity Assessment at regional level: EU project MARIE](#) was organised with the objective to extract valuable knowledge and strategies that will help in the development of regionally co-created RRI evaluation tools in TRANSFORM. Presented by Giulia Bubbolini, the session was attended by TRANSFORM partners, and fruitful discussion followed. The recording of the session is also available in the TRANSFORM video library for wider audience to benefit from it.
- TRANSFORM (notably UiB), [SeeRRI](#) and [SuperMoRRI](#) created in June-July 2020 an initiative to exchange and coordinate experiences with RRI monitoring and evaluation across all SwafS-14-funded actions. This has resulted in dedicated workshops with all SwafS-14 actions and a series of bimonthly regular meetings with SwafS-14 actions as part of the RRI ecosystem initiative of SuperMoRRI. UiB, FGB and BePart have taken part in these meetings.
- TRANSFORM (notably UiB) collaborates and exchanges updates on methodological development with [SuperMoRRI](#) on a regular basis, notably with SuperMoRRI WP5 leader IHS in Vienna.
- A bilateral meeting between TRANSFORM and [RRI2SCALE](#) coordinators (FGB and APRE) has been organised to discuss the chance to co-organise events in Italy on RRI and its implementation at national level.
- A contact was made with [SeeRRI](#) and [DigiTeRRI](#) and AEIDL to explore a synergistic collaboration between the three projects for communication and dissemination actions.
- On 9 February 2021, GenCat explored synergies with the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona within the [INCENTIVE project](#). UAB is participating in Transform pilot projects and Gencat is participating in some INCENTIVE activities promoted by UAB.

M16-M36

- AEIDL prepared a poster for the [NewHoRRizon Final Conference](#), which was presented by FGB during the online session on 20 May 2021.
- During the [European Research and Innovation days](#) (23-24 June 2021), TRANSFORM video was presented in the video gallery at the [JRC House](#) within the Horizon Village, in the corner with the External links, following ‘the Spotlight on JRC: the European Commission’s science and knowledge service’.

- FGB presented experiences of citizen engagement, including TRANSFORM, to [UKUH](#) consortium on 21 July 2021.
- Several partners took part in “[SeeRRI Final Conference “Bringing RRI into regional planning: From theory to SeeRRI”](#) held in Barcelona on 29 - 30 September 2021, and related activities. Angela Simone (FGB) took part in a session ‘Impact of cross-project collaboration’. together with Nhien Nguyen ([SeeRRI](#) Project Coordinator) and & Marianne Hörlesberger ([DigiTeRRI](#) Project Coordinator). On the second day, Marzia Mazzonetto (BE participation), took part in a session ‘How mutual learning happens between regions in EU projects’ together with Elisabetta Marinelli (Advisory Board member in [SeeRRI](#)) and Tanja Adnađević ([TeRRIFICA project](#)). Moreover, AEIDL prepared a poster which was presented by TRANSFORM partners during the conference and together with FGB, prepared a contribution on behalf of TRANSFORM to the [SeeRRI booklet](#).
- FGB engaged in a cooperation with OECD – Open Government, Civic Space and Public Communication Unit on the development of the the Italian translation of the Highlights 2020 of the OECD report “[Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions: Catching the Deliberative Wave](#)”, and organisation of a [launch event](#) to present it. The launch event took place on 25 October 2021 (online) in cooperation with OECD, JRC Ispra, National Commission for Public Debate – Italian Ministry of Sustainable Infrastructure and Mobility (Italy), Lombardy Region, Directorate General for Education, University, Research, Innovation and Simplification, and Emilia-Romagna Region, General Directorate for the Economy of Knowledge, Labour and Business Communication channels and tools. The Italian translation of the report is available (open access) on the TRANSFORM website and Open Innovation (Lombardy) website. It aims to provide the Italian policy makers and interested stakeholders with an instrument to navigate opportunities, methodologies, and best practices of citizen engagement and deliberation.
- FGB engaged in a cooperation with the OECD - Committee for Scientific and Technological Policy (CSTP) and its Working Party on Bio-, Nano- and Converging Technologies (BNCT) during the summer and autumn of 2021, in preparation of the OECD High-Level conference “[Technology in and for Society](#)” on 6-7 December 2021 in which Bassetti Foundation was involved. **Panel 1.** “Building inclusivity upstream: engaging diverse actors in the development of emerging technology” , was chaired by **Dr. Angela Simone, FGB's International Initiatives Scientific Coordinator and TRANSFORM coordinator.**
- On 12 October 2021, TRANSFORM organised a participatory lab titled ‘[Citizen engagement TRANSFORMing regional R&I policymaking](#)’, within the European Week of Regions and Cities. Project partners FGB, BEpart and SfC briefly presented the three TRANSFORM citizen engagement methodologies, then engaged in an open discussion with participants.
- TRANSFORM partners took part in the [GRACE Final Webinar series](#). BEpart presented TRANSFORM in a session ‘[Making the case for public engagement](#)’ on 2 November 2021, while SfC presented TRANSFORM experience in Catalonia in the session [on Public Engagement: The research funders’ perspective](#) on 16 November 2021.
- FGB took part in the TeRRItoria's #ResponsibleRegions, a series of monthly webinars organised by TeRRItoria project, in a dedicated session “[TRANSFORM. Giving citizens a](#)

[seat at the table of R&I regional policymaking. The Lombardy region case](#)” which took place online on 16 December 2021.

- TRANSFORM (UiB) was also taking part in the monthly “SwafS14 Monitoring & Evaluation” meetings, promoted by the SUPER MoRRI project. During those meetings, we have been exchanging with several other SwafS-14 projects about experiences and best practices in fostering more open, transparent, and democratic R&I ecosystems in Europe. The cooperation resulted in the joint abstract “What is territorial RRI? A discussion of issues, tensions and lessons learned in monitoring and evaluation practices based on nine H2020 projects” which was selected for the [REvaluation conference](#) in Vienna.
- FGB also presented TRANSFORM during the TeRRitoria’s Final Conference: RRI institutional changes for improved regional governance, in an online session [“How to engage citizens in regional development policies”](#) organised on 18 January 2022.
- A presentation of TRANSFORM was provided at the internal meeting to INCENTIVE project by Sfc on 31 May 2022.
- On 1 June 2022, FGB gave a presentation on citizens’ engagement as tool for responsible R&I governance to POCYTIF project.
- AEIDL contributed to the [newsletter](#) of the [WBC-RRI.NET: Embedding RRI in Western Balkan Countries: Enhancement of Self-Sustaining R&I Ecosystems](#) with the overview of the TRANSFORM project pointing out relevant results and activities to stakeholders from all over Europe, including Western Balkans.
- Cooperation with [ENJOI project](#) and [MOSAIC project](#) resulted into a joint poster presentation at the [ESOF conference](#) (13 – 16 July 2022) in Leiden. While AEIDL prepared the poster, FGB presented it at the conference.
- [TRANSFORM video](#) was selected for the participation in the project exhibition during the [4th Public Participation and Deliberative Democracy Festival](#) organised by JRC (20 – 21 October 2022).
- TRANSFORM Final Conference gave space to other projects to present their work in a poster presentation during the two days event in Milan. [MOSAIC project](#), [BRIDGES – Building Reflexivity and response-ability Involving Different narratives of knowledGES](#), [ENJOI \(ENGagement and JOurnalism Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication\)](#), [FETA – Fair Energy Transition for All](#), and Participatory initiatives for transforming and developing the Italian mountains in a sustainable way took part in the poster presentation.
- During the TRANSFORM Final Conference, the space was provided to citizen and multistakeholder engagement initiatives at EU level with the territorial focus to present their work and activities: the [Future of Europe Conference](#) and the role of regions and cities in this context, bringing the experience of capacity building and support for local citizen participation processes, a [joint project](#) of the [Bertelsmann Stiftung Foundation with the Committee of the Regions](#). DG Regio shared their experiences with [“Engaging citizens in cohesion policy”](#) on how to engage citizens in decision-making processes for policy making and the [EU Teens4Green](#) project, which has launched a call to promote the participation of youth from different European regions in the just energy transition. [The European Regions Research and Innovation Network \(ERRIN\)](#), presented the NetZero

Cities, [MOSAIC](#) project, and the [CrAft](#) (Creating Actionable Futures) platform. The European Commission's Joint Research Centre in Seville introduced Partnerships for Regional Innovation (PRI), a pilot process and potential successor to S3, and mentioned some of the tools, including the recently published "[Partnerships for Regional Innovation Playbook](#)", and the Open Discovery Process.

Communication channels and tools

The communication and dissemination channels were selected to convey the key messages and outcomes of the project to the largest possible number of stakeholders and target group members. The strategy worked through both information pull and information push and included various tools designed to reach different kinds of target groups.

Visual Identity

The visual identity was delivered in M6 and it has been consistently used since throughout various channels and products. Visual identity was at the heart of establishing a coherent and consistent image for the project.

The **Communication Toolkit** consists of:

- Visual style guide
- Logo (in various formats)
- Three cluster logos and one international partner logo (in various formats)
- Visual identity elements for website (Banner, video for banner)
- Social media banners (LinkedIn, Twitter)
- Templates for minutes and reports
- Template for PowerPoint presentations
- Template for WP deliverables

The project brochure providing an overview of the project in English was produced by M15. The brochure is available on the project website.

Website

www.transform-project.eu

The first version of the website was launched in M4, providing essential information about the project. The information was revised over time, and more pages were created as the project implementation progressed. The work on the website continued throughout the project, incorporating sections and content according to needs and informing about the progress of project activities. Technical maintenance including specific attention to security was ensured throughout the duration of the project.

The website serves as the first point of contact with the project for a wide audience, presenting its scope, activities and progress. At the same time, it represents the main communication and dissemination channel ensuring visibility and outreach, regularly updating the audience on activities within the project but also relevant news, documents and activities related to the topics relevant to TRANSFORM.

Design of the website was based on the following technical features and characteristics:

- A user-friendly and attractive interface, open to the public of potential users and different stakeholders
- Clear structure, easy navigation, evoking positive, encouraging emotions
- Optimised for all types of mobile devices (phones, tablets for both iOS and Android operating systems)
- Fully accessible by all users following the requirement for [W3C](#) compliance
- GDPR compliant, including all GDPR-related features (privacy consent for all forms, consent for cookies on a first visit, etc.)
- SEO-optimisation of pages
- Search facility on the site
- Offer a contact point
- Links to social media channels
- Web Analytics provided via [Matomo](#), an open-source platform with 100% data ownership and GDPR compliance.

Website structure

The website structure reflected the needs of the project, all work packages and partners while ensuring clear and intuitive navigation. To ensure the provision of information in a consistent and clear manner, all partners were invited to share their needs and vision on the structure of the website – a site map – presented during the kick-off meeting.

Slight changes have been applied, including the development of additional pages, subpages or elements, since further needs have arisen throughout the implementation of the project. Additional resources will still be uploaded after M36, notably the approved deliverables and potentially some translations of other resources (e.g. executive summaries of the strategic roadmaps).

Webpages for the Final Conference were developed, accessible from the main website and structured into a specific sub-menu. It followed the simple structure:

- Home page
- Agenda
- Call for posters

- Practical information

Final version of the site map is included in Annex I.

Technical development and maintenance

The website was developed internally by AEIDL, coded using a leading content management system – WordPress. The website is hosted on the computer servers of AEIDL, allowing flexibility for web-development and dynamic functionality. The technical maintenance was ensured by AEIDL, content management – using an open-source Content Management System – lies fully under AEIDL with contribution from all partners. The content was regularly updated throughout the implementation of the project. All partners' logos are clearly visible at the bottom of the website with links to their websites along with the EC logo and acknowledgment of the EU funds in line with the visual guidelines of the European Commission.

The website will be kept alive by AEIDL for 2 years following the closure of the project, until 31 December 2024.

Search Engine Optimisation (SEO)

The website uses Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) techniques, with selected keywords, key phrases and extensive tagging to improve visibility. To achieve high visibility for the website in organic search, AEIDL deployed techniques such as writing keyword-rich page titles and adding description meta tags; including keywords in headers, positioning keywords in the first paragraph of the body text and using keywords in hyperlinks, etc.

Website analytics

To monitor the website analytics, Matomo analytics was installed in October 2020 as an ethical alternative without making privacy sacrifices or compromising the site. Matomo is the Google Analytics alternative that protects data and visitors' privacy, providing 100% data ownership. Before that, simple analytical tools provided by WordPress were used to monitor traffic on the website.

The graphs below provide an overview of website traffic for the first reporting period M1 - M15. We reached 3,891 visits with 90% of visitors coming from Europe.

Figure 2: Website analytics - October 2020 - 12 March 2021 (M10-M15)

Figure 3: Website analytics: Visitors map October 2020 - 12 March 2021 (M10-M15)

Summary	
Hits	
Total Hits	168,018
Visitor Hits	161,228
Spider Hits	6,790
Average Hits per Day	1,070
Average Hits per Visitor	54.60
Cached Requests	9,791
Failed Requests	1,856
Page Views	
Total Page Views	101,094
Average Page Views per Day	643
Average Page Views per Visitor	34.23
Visitors	
Total Visitors	2,953
Average Visitors per Day	18
Total Unique IPs	2,603
Bandwidth	
Total Bandwidth	1.51 GB
Visitor Bandwidth	1.42 GB
Spider Bandwidth	85.85 MB
Average Bandwidth per Day	9.83 MB
Average Bandwidth per Hit	9.41 KB
Average Bandwidth per Visitor	505.45 KB

Figure 4: Website analytics - April 2020- October 2020 (M4-M10)

The following graphs show the website analytics for the second reporting period from M16 to M36. We reached 11,486 visits with 68.5% of visitors coming from Europe. Therefore, in total, TRANSFORM project website received more than 15,000 visitors over the three years.

Figure 5: Website analytics April 2021 - December 2022 (M16-M36)

Figure 6: Website analytics - visitors map - April 2021 - December 2022 (M15-M36)

Social media

Social media channels were used to increase the awareness of potential users, spark interest about the project and the topic of territorial RRI, and encourage them to take part in project activities, events as well as download the project's outputs. Each channel was intended to reach a specific audience, and the messages are adapted accordingly. Social media was intended to act as an accelerator of the discussion and to direct the traffic to project website. Two social media channels were set up for the project to reaching out to a wide and relevant audience. The content shared on each platform included different types of outputs and redirected and feeds traffic to the main website.

Supporting visual materials (pictures, banners, gifs, videos) were used in order to highlight messages. Appealing visuals helped catch the attention of the followers/audience and invited them to read more and learn more about the proposed topic. For instance, video teasers/gifs shared on social media invite the target audience to read more. The illustrative elements, such as banners, help create brand consistency and visual identity for the project.

TRANSFORM focused on two social media channels – **Twitter and LinkedIn**. Although initially Facebook account was also foreseen in the proposal stage, the consortium decided to focus the efforts on two more popular and relevant social media channels among our target audience. Over the past years, Facebook has been falling in popularity and became prone to quick spread of disinformation and hate speech. In addition, it has become rather difficult to build an active and engaged community on Facebook, especially within, and only for, a limited time of 36 months with frequent changes in algorithm which favour paid promotion. Instead,

Twitter account helped us to reach and connect with EU institutions, public authorities, scientific community and EU-funded projects, maximising dissemination of the results and raising visibility of the project. Moreover, a LinkedIn group was set up with an aim to invite and bring together professionals, EU-funded projects working on territorial RRI, relevant initiatives and key stakeholders to create a space to exchange and share knowledge, experience and lessons learned, explore synergies and foster networking. In addition, a specific [YouTube channel](#) was set up for the project, hosting videos created within the project.

The Social Media Guidelines were prepared by AIEDL and shared with partners at the beginning of the project (M4) to help them communicate about the project effectively and consistently on social media.

Twitter

Handle: [@TRANSFORM_eu](#)

Hashtags: #TRANSFORM #RRI #CitizenEngagement #CitizenParticipation #SmartSpecialisation #delibwave #H2020 #SwafS #TerritorialDevelopment #Reseach #Innovation #CitizenScience #MultistakeholderEngagement #ParticipatoryResearchAgenda

Figure 7: TRANSFORM Twitter account

This channel was used for short news flashes, using a clear and crisp style, not too descriptive nor institutional. Twitter allows rapid communication between professionals, organisations and media. It is a real-time communication tool. It allows tweeting questions and having followers respond within a few seconds. Twitter is a major social media network used at the

EU level within the European institutions, EU projects, umbrella organisations, international organisations, public authorities and academia. Thus, Twitter was the most relevant social media platform for TRANSFORM.

Offering only short messages – 280 characters – Twitter is known as a highly paced network demanding frequent activity and updates in order to maintain an active and attractive profile. Retweets enable sharing of interesting content generated by other users as well as the possibility to easily spread messages to a wide audience.

Twitter is deploying key messages in a short, catchy manner using visual support (pictures, banners, infographics, short video clips, etc.) informing on the latest developments, news articles, publication of new documents, disseminating results and findings and promoting networking. Events are promoted via Twitter and pictures/videos and/or compelling quotes shared during the event. At the same time, it directs traffic to the project website.

As Twitter was a high-paced social media network, around 3-5 posts are published per week. The Twitter account was set up in April 2020 (M4). Until now 19 December 2022 (M36), TRANSFORM's Twitter account **counts 820 followers and 1045 tweets**, therefore around 8 tweets per week. Twitter analytics show an increasing number of the followers over the duration of the project with the range of **impressions between 10 – 48k per quarter** and **engagement rate between 1% at the beginning of the project, reaching up to 5.7% towards the end of the project**. See Twitter statistic overview below for further information.

Figure 8: Twitter analytics April - June 2020

Figure 9: Twitter analytics July - September 2020

Figure 10: Twitter analytics October - December 2020

Figure 11: Twitter analytics January - March 2021

Your Tweets earned **48.6K impressions** over this **91 day period**

Figure 12: Twitter analytics March 2021 - June 2021

Your Tweets earned **38.5K impressions** over this **91 day period**

Figure 13: Twitter analytics June 2021 - September 2021

Your Tweets earned **26.6K impressions** over this **91 day period**

Figure 14: Twitter analytics September 2021 - December 2021

Your Tweets earned **13.2K impressions** over this **91 day period**

Figure 15: Twitter analytics December 2021 - March 2022

Your Tweets earned **14.5K impressions** over this **91 day period**

YOUR TWEETS
During this 91 day period, you earned **159 impressions** per day.

Tweets Top Tweets Tweets and replies Promoted Impressions Engagements Engagement rate

TRANSFORM @TRANSFORM_eu · Jun 13

Check out the thread of @SciencefChange on their participation in the #EntreDones conference to share & learn about #women's #health from an integrative perspective. An opportunity to shake hands with health professionals and women 🤝

#endometriosis #citizenscience
twitter.com/SciencefChange

Impressions	Engagements	Engagement rate
220	8	3.6%

Engagements
Showing 91 days with daily frequency

Figure 16: Twitter analytics March 2022 - June 2022

Your Tweets earned **11.5K impressions** over this **91 day period**

YOUR TWEETS
During this 91 day period, you earned **126 impressions** per day.

Tweets Top Tweets Tweets and replies Promoted Impressions Engagements Engagement rate

TRANSFORM @TRANSFORM_eu · Sep 12

#TRANSFORM participatory process in #Brussels-Capital will conclude on (4) Oct w/ a workshop to consider common solutions for the management of unsold food with public authorities @Innoviris associations, private actors and citizens.

#RRI #citizenengagement @BeParticipation

Impressions	Engagements	Engagement rate
98	5	5.1%

Engagements
Showing 91 days with daily frequency

Figure 17: Twitter analytics June 2022 - September 2022

Your Tweets earned **20.5K impressions** over this **93 day period**

Figure 18: Twitter analytics - September 2022 - December 2022

LinkedIn

Group name: 'Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation'

Link: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13853941/>

Figure 19: LinkedIn group

Being a social network for professionals, LinkedIn allows the creation of dedicated communities and groups to discuss specific topics and spread information to a wide professional audience. Based on this, a group has been created with a view to connecting with key stakeholders as well as relevant projects and initiatives to build synergies and foster knowledge transfer. Selected articles, news pieces and other communications content will also be shared on this platform. Via LinkedIn, TRANSFORM host a permanent group

(membership on request) community to create a space to foster exchange among its members, share experiences, events, studies, news and relevant information with peers.

The group was set up in the second year of the project when the activities started to be further developed. The group invited professionals, projects and initiatives working on RRI and especially those representing projects funded under the H2020 call 'SwafS-14-2018-2019-2020 - Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation'. AEIDL moderated and managed the LinkedIn group, posting 1-2 posts per week of relevant content related to RRI topics, citizen engagement including events, publications, articles, podcasts and relevant materials.

Although, efforts were deployed to promote the group via personalised mailing to targeted audience and direct invitations sent via LinkedIn, the group did not generate as much interest as foreseen. To 19 December, the group counts 63 members. This might be caused overall general digital fatigue followed the pandemic of Covid-19 and consequent switch to online work and meetings, and/or the fact that each project has its own social media channels for the project.

YouTube

YouTube channel name: TRANSFORM project

Link: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC0Tw8auUBj2MtOYMeX2Ol-w>

Figure 20: TRANSFORM YouTube channel

A YouTube channel was created (M12) for TRANSFORM to host videos created within the project. Currently, there are 24 videos and has 17 followers.

- [Project animation](#) – published 01/12/2020, updated version following the review meeting published on 26 August 2021 with the total of 464 views ([309 views](#) + [80 views](#) of an updated video following the 1st review meeting, and version with subtitles in [Italian](#), [French](#), [Dutch](#) and [Catalan](#).; with 859 impressions, 14,75% impressions click-through rate) – presenting the project and regional clusters to general public in a visually appealing and easy-to-understand format.

Figure 21: Project animation - YouTube analytics

- [Citizen engagement TRANSFORMing regional R&I policy making](#) – 2nd official project video presenting TRANSFORM journey over the three years of the project implementation, project activities, results and impact. The video was initially published on 15/10/2022 to be showcased at the online project exhibition at the 4th Public Participation and Deliberative Democracy Festival (28 views). [A longer version](#) was published on 29/11/2022 with subtitles available in English, Italian, French and Catalan. Impressions: 275; Click-through rate: 8,45%

Figure 22: 2nd project video - YouTube analytics

As many project meetings were held in online format due to the Covid-19 pandemic, AEIDL decided to create an [additional video during the TRANSFORM Final Conference](#) in Milan, which was also an opportunity for all partners to gather.

Moreover, the YouTube channel host the recordings of capacity building session which were organised online throughout the three years of the implementation of the project. The sessions are saved in the TRANSFORM Capacity Building playlist. All sessions are also featured in a [video library](#) on the website and promoted via social media.

- TRANSFORM capacity building session no.1: The methodology of the RRI Maturity Assessment at regional level: EU project MARIE – published on 09/03/2021 - (77 views, 446 impressions, 3.8% impressions click-through rate).

- [TRANSFORM capacity building session no.2: Collaboration with CSOs for citizen engagement](#) – published on 14/07/2021 - (53 views, 255 impressions, 6.3% impressions click-through rate).
- [TRANSFORM capacity building session no.3: Citizen Science \(Louise Francis\)](#) – published on 22/03/2022 – (28 views, 269 impressions, 4.5 % impressions click-through rate).
- [TRANSFORM capacity building session no.4: Participative Innovation Agenda Setting \(Simon Burall\)](#) – published on 20/07/2022 – (37 views, 210 impressions, 6.2 % impressions click-through rate).
- [TRANSFORM capacity building session no.5: Social innovation, participation and local development \(Anna Meroni\)](#) – published on 01/12/2022 – (11 views, 147 impressions, 0.7% impressions click-through rate).

Two videos produced by Lombardy regional cluster:

- [TRANSFORM - Deliberative engagement in Lombardy Region](#) – describing the first strand of the citizen engagement activities in Lombardy using participatory research agenda setting. The video animation presents the survey and deliberative workshop on just energy transition, results and impact on regional policy. The video was published on 18/07/2022. Views: 66 views; Impressions: 184 impressions; Impressions click-through rate: 8.7%.
- [TRANSFORM - Citizen Jury in Lombardy](#) – describing the second strand of the citizen engagement activities in Lombardy, organisation of the Citizen Jury, on Responsible Data-driven Smart Mobility emerging results and impact on regional policy. The video was published on 01/09/2022. Views: 148 views; Impressions: 334; Impressions click-through rate: 5.1%.

Two videos presenting the approach and activities of the Brussels-Capital regional cluster published by BE participation were placed in the TRANSFORM project video playlist:

- [TRANSFORM dans la région de Bruxelles-Capitale / in het Brussels Hoofdstedelijk Gewest](#) – 112 views
- [TRANSFORM dans la région de Bruxelles-Capitale - in het Brussels Hoofdstedelijk Gewest - short](#) – 42 views

In addition, the YouTube channels hosts the following videos produced during the project:

- [“Catching the deliberative wave - Highlights 2020” – launch of the Italian translation](#) – recording from the launch session
- Promotional video [Join TRANSFORM participatory lab at #EURegionsWeek](#)
- [La voce dei cittadini nelle politiche regionali di Ricerca e Innovazione](#) – recording from the regional final event in Lombardy
- [TRANSFORM Final Conference](#) – five recordings put together in a playlist.

AEIDL also created a playlist [‘TRANSFORM at events and conferences’](#) putting together recordings of various sessions in which TRANSFORM was presented, e.g. TeRRItoria final conference, TeRRItoria’s #ResponsibleRegions, Grace webinars, etc.

TRANSFORM social media main contents

The above-mentioned social media channels were used to maximise the visibility, dissemination and further exploitation (when possible) of the following content:

- Project objectives, activities and benefits
- Presentation of TRANSFORM partners
- Findings from reports and deliverables
- Presenting clusters in depth – activities, results, outcomes, impact
- Presentation of used methodologies and their benefits
- Presenting mutual learning concept and capacity building sessions
- Presenting TRANSFORM approach to monitoring and evaluation
- Showcasing good practices related to territorial RRI, especially those focusing on public engagement
- Promoting events in which TRANSFORM participated, events organised by TRANSFORM
- Sharing videos
- Sharing interesting news from partners
- Disseminating public deliverables, materials and results
- Promoting relevant EU, national, regional and local events
- Cross-promotion with other projects and initiatives
- Sharing relevant news, publications, training opportunities and events.

Multimedia production

Videos

Animation

A short animation was developed and delivered in M11, published in M12. The initial duration was planned to be around 1 minute, but to cover the complete picture of the project presenting each cluster, we decided to go for a longer format – 2.22 minutes. The script was prepared by and agreed upon among AEIDL and cluster leaders, using an easy-to-understand, non-technical language and visually appealing form targeting a wide, non-technical audience. The animation includes ‘Call to action’ – Together for more open, inclusive and democratic R&I – and prompts viewers to learn more about TRANSFORM by visiting the website and join us on social media.

The animation was made in Adobe After Effects, it was made of a combination of bespoke vector images constructed in Adobe Illustrator, hand-drawn elements that were scanned and

turned into vectors and stock photographs. The technical style of the video is known as 2.5D - this is where 2D images are positioned in 3D space, and a 'virtual camera' is created to zoom through this virtual space, creating the impression of true 3D via shifts in perspective lines. The video was exported as an h264 format MP4, in full HD (1920 X 1080), in 24 frames a second. This format was selected because it is very high quality but lightweight, making it easy and quick to transfer, upload and host.

TRANSFORM animation was selected for the virtual exhibition, showcased during the [3rd Citizen Engagement and Deliberative Democracy Festival](#), taking place from 6 to 12 December 2020, organised by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission. The video is published on the TRANSFORM YouTube channel, as well as on the project website.

Video: <https://youtu.be/Yqs1O8zeWY8>

Final video

In summer 2022, AEIDL started the development of the final video in cooperation with cluster leaders. The objective of the video is to present the TRANSFORM journey in a concise, easy-to-understand way using footage from clusters and project activities combined with animations and visuals. The video takes the viewer through the activities and results of three regional clusters and their impact on regional R&I policies and governance. Mutual learning within and beyond three regions, with CC-PES project in the US. The video conveys a message to inspire local authorities and practitioners to work together to implement RRI in their R&I activities, putting an emphasis on the TRANSFORM results – [project e-book](#), strategic roadmaps – and the **'Call to action' prompting viewers to use these results and implement RRI in their regional context.**

The visual identity of the project was incorporated in the video, ensuring consistency and coherence. An initial version of 3 minutes was selected for the publication during the online project exhibition during the 4th Public Participation and Deliberative Democracy Festival organised by JRC on 20 and 21 October 2022. The longer version was then published with the total length of 3'40 minutes.

The video is published on the TRANSFORM's YouTube channel and project website. The subtitles are available in English, Italian, French and Catalan. It was shared on social media,

presented during the TRANSFORM Final Conference, and further disseminated via the partners' channels and multipliers.

Video: <https://youtu.be/qJiXGZK3Wrk>

RRI and citizen engagement to open up regional R&I policymaking

The final conference was a great opportunity for all partners to meet (Due to Covid-19 only one consortium meeting was held in person), and further, convey key messages of the TRANSFORM project. AEIDL, therefore, decided to create an additional project video during the conference, giving space to project partners to present their TRANSFORMative journey, activities, benefits and impact. With the objective **to promote territorial RRI and citizen engagement in (regional) R&I policy and governance** to create policies more aligned with citizens' needs, values and aspirations, the video targets policy makers, public authorities and RRI practitioners

A 3 minutes video showing key moments and atmosphere of the conference with short interviews of project partners on transformative potential, added value and impact of territorial RRI and citizen engagement in regional R&I policy making and governance, conveying the message of practical examples implemented in three regional clusters in the framework of TRANSFORM. **Call for action:** Get inspired by TRANSFORM and embark on a participation journey.

The video is published on the TRANSFORM's YouTube channel and project website and it was shared via social media and direct mailing.

Video: <https://youtu.be/g6waHXcPw-k>

Capacity building sessions recordings

Due to current restrictions imposed by public authorities to halt the spread of Covid-19, capacity building sessions have been organised online via Zoom. We took this as an opportunity to record the sessions and make them available for a larger audience. The recordings are thus edited (adding introductory and closing slides) and published on the TRANSFORM's YouTube channel. A [video library](#) for capacity building sessions has been

created on the project website, also providing a short overview for each session. The video library will be regularly updated as sessions take place.

Cluster videos

Lombardy regional cluster created two videos explaining their participatory activities:

[TRANSFORM - Deliberative engagement in Lombardy Region](#) – first deliberative exercise collecting experiences and opinions on personal and territorial needs from Lombardy's citizens to contribute to shaping regional R&I priorities through a survey and deliberative workshop on just energy transition. Video uses animations and graphics as the activities took place online.

[TRANSFORM – Citizens' Jury in Lombardy](#) - the second stream of deliberative engagement - Citizen Jury on Responsible Data-Driven Smart Mobility. Video uses footage from the Citizen Jury and interviews with implementing project partners from the Lombardy region and citizens taking part in the Jury.

Catalonia developed two pilots presenting their activities and results of two pilot projects – waste and health pilots - using citizen science and participatory research in Catalonia. Videos use footage from project activities, interviews with project partners implementing of Catalan cluster as well as representatives or local organisations and citizens who took part in the pilot projects.

Brussels-Capital developed two videos in French and with English subtitles, explaining RRI and the need for citizen engagement, describing the implemented approach and the first pilot 'Aguasense'. These two videos feature project partners of the Brussels-Capital regional cluster and innovators from the pilot project.

[TRANSFORM dans la région de Bruxelles-Capitale / in het Brussels Hoofdstedelijk Gewest](#)
(long version)

[TRANSFORM dans la région de Bruxelles-Capitale / in het Brussels Hoofdstedelijk Gewest](#)
(short version)

Photo shoot

Professional photos were taken during project meetings and the Final Conference by FGB. The photo gallery is available on the project website and the pictures were shared through

project social media channels. Due to the pandemics, several project meetings were organised online and photo shooting in person were therefore not possible. A [photo gallery](#) is available from the following meeting:

- Online consortium meeting I 28 – 29 September 2020
- Project meeting in Barcelona I 5 – 6 May 2022
- TRANSFORM Final Conference I 1 – 2 December 2022

Hybrid final conference

A webinar was foreseen at the end of the project (M35) to foster an interactive learning environment in which stakeholders felt involved. The idea behind the webinar was to present the outcomes and results of the project to inspire other regions to take up the RRI approach in their R&I activities, provide guidelines and share knowledge on how to implement tested methodologies, draw attention to barriers, benefits and lessons learned. The final goal was to lead to further uptake of the project results and maximise its impact.

Based on a series of reflections, TRANSFORM partners decided to organise the final conference as a hybrid event (in person and online) so as to couple the final event with the webinar. This decision was also to respond to different needs and take into consideration external factors, such as increased energy prices and inflation, Covid-19 and flu wave, busy agendas of policymakers in December.

The online conference has been fully recorded. Recordings and material (slides) from two days are available on the project's [Youtube channel](#) and [website](#).

During the conference, the Zoom chat was administered by FGB to engage online participants, share documents/links/questions to better frame the discussion, and bridge with the offline conference. A list of relevant links was listed by FGB before the conference and then shared based on the flow of the discussion, adding also more resources when they popped up in the conversation. The chat with comments and questions was also displayed on the screens onsite at the end of each relevant session during Q&A time.

Media

The purpose of using general and specialised media content is to reach both the general public and a more specific audience with key information in the field of regional R&I, RRI and S3. The subscription to Anewstip provided an extensive media contact database and allow the monitoring of news articles. We used partners' existing media contact lists to develop

and implement press and public relations activities. AEIDL used the Anewstip to create media lists (outlets and journalists) for the project and regional clusters to send out press releases.

Press release

A press release is a statement distributed to the media to generate interest and thus press coverage on specific news. Press releases are written communication that should be issued when the project is doing something new, interesting, or different that would be of interest to local, national or European media. It is important to target the audience of the press release, keep it short and make sure that it has sufficient news value to compete with other news in a rather busy environment. When developing the press release it is vital to consider the audience. An audience analysis will determine the tone, style, angle and content of the article. Press releases also have an impact on our future website's searchability, appearing in search results and encouraging media outlets to create backlinks to our site.

The **first press release** was launched via Anewstip on 16/03/2021 summarising the first year of TRANSFORM, its main achievements and next steps. AEIDL curated a list of 827 recipients - journalists and media outlets covering EU27+UK, using keywords search on topics covered by TRANSFORM (citizen engagement; responsible research and innovations; Smart Specialisation; public engagement; stakeholder engagement; citizen participation; deliberative democracy; deliberative wave; social sciences; democracy).

The regional final events were accompanied by a press release in national/local language, distributed to curated media list at the regional level. Location and key words (citizen engagement; responsible research and innovations (RRI); Smart Specialisation; public engagement; stakeholder engagement; citizen participation; deliberative democracy; deliberative wave; social sciences; democracy; Europe and other relevant to the regional activities) were used to build the regional media lists to select relevant outlets/journalists. The press releases used clear language and journalistic style, and were accompanied by a visual created for each regional event using regional TRANSFORM logos in line with the visual identity. Links to the project website and social media were added for more information.

Lombardy

La voce dei cittadini nelle politiche di regionali di Ricerca e Innovazione

Media list: 68 contacts Open rate: 11.86%

Brussels-Capital

Engagement multipartite dans la gouvernance de la Recherche & Innovation de Bruxelles-Capitale (Brussels-Capital)

Media list: 49 contacts Open rate: 44.9%

Catalonia

La veu de la ciutadania en l'elaboració de polítiques de R+D a Catalunya

Media list: 46 contacts Open rate: 19.57%

A press release/invite also accompanied the final event, inviting outlets/journalists to join the event. A media list was created targeting English speaking outlets and journalists covering topics on democracy, citizen participation, or responsible research and innovation. In addition to the language, the media list was built around keywords (and key words (citizen engagement; responsible research and innovations (RRI), Smart Specialisation; public engagement; stakeholder engagement; citizen participation; deliberative democracy; deliberative wave; social sciences; democracy; Europe). Inviting, using journalistic style and attractive visual, the press release provided main information about the event and details links for the further information about the conference. The press release was sent to 110 contacts with an open rate of 19.09%.

Press releases are also published on the [TRANSFORM website](#).

Publications

A number of publications stemmed from the TRANSFORM project activities and results. A popularised article published in a renowned digital magazine Nature Italy, an Italian translation of the OECD report Catching the deliberative wave, two scientific publications and a book authored by the UiB colleagues, resulting from the work done in WP7 Monitoring and Evaluation led by UiB.

[Give citizens a seat at the table](#) by Angela Simone & Mario Calderini

Participatory methods and social innovation improve trust in science, and ensure that research meets social needs. They should be more widely adopted in Italy.

An article '[Give citizens a seat at the table](#)', co-authored by the TRANSFORM Project Coordinator, Angela Simone (FGB) on citizen engagement and social innovation and their potential to shape the future of R&I in Italy. The article was recently published in [Nature Italy](#), the regional digital magazine, published by Springer Nature, reporting on scientific research and issues of science policy in Italy.

[Innovazione nella partecipazione dei cittadini al decision making pubblico e nuove istituzioni democratiche. Cavalcare l'onda della deliberazione](#)

The Italian translation of the OECD report: Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions | Catching the deliberative wave

The Italian version of the Highlights 2020 of the OECD report "[Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions: Catching the Deliberative Wave](#)" aims to contribute to spreading the culture of public deliberation and provide effective tools for citizen engagement in public policy making in Italy.

Scientific publications submitted by UiB:

- T. Völker, R. Slaattelid & R. Strand: "Transformative Translations? Challenges and tensions in territorial innovation governance", submitted to the Journal "[Novation - Critical Studies of Innovation](#)"
- T. Völker, M. Mazzonetto, R. Slaattelid & R. Strand: "Translating tools and indicators in territorial RRI", submitted to the Journal "[Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics](#)"

UiB is finalising a book with the preliminary title "**Innovation Governance in Three European Regions: Translations of Responsibility**", authored by Roger Strand, Rasmus Slaattelid and Thomas Völker. The book will be published by [Routledge](#).

Moreover, the **Catalan cluster** is working on article submission to be submitted/published in Dec 2022 and early 2023:

- Article on health pilot with the preliminary title "**First-person experiences of endometriosis in Catalonia: recommendations of women with endometriosis for improving health care services and public policies.**" will be published in early 2023 in [Frontiers](#) by *Nora Salas and Diana Reinoso (SfC)*
- [La implicació de la ciutadania en les agendes compartides de la RIS3CAT 2030](#) by *Tatiana Fernández (GENCAT)*

- [Aprentatges del projecte TRANSFORM](#) by Tatiana Fernández and Sergio Martínez (GENCAT)

The Brussels cluster has published a report (available in French, Dutch and English) summarizing key outcomes of their Unsold Food pilot process, and focusing in particular on future potential uptakes at public and private level. The report is available on the cluster leader website, BE participation asbl:

- [“Les principes de la Recherche et Innovation Responsable \(RRI\) appliques a l’ecosysteme d’innovations autour des invendus alimentaires”](#), by Marzia Mazzonetto, Fabien Lambert and Maite Debry

-

BE participation is also working on a scientific publication focused on the analysis of the citizen engagement workshops carried out within the Unsold food pilot.

Events

Table 4 provides a summary of the events organised within the project. To ensure effective communication and dissemination of the different actions, developments and results carried out, the table also details communications elements implemented during these events.

Table 4: TRANSFORM-organised events

Type of event	Objective	Target audience	Communication
Local Final Events M35	To present and disseminate the results of the project in each regional cluster; summarise and present the activities, outcomes and impact at regional level; build a strong, long-lasting and engaged network beyond the duration of the project.	Regional and national stakeholders, Think Tank members, policy makers, CSOs, NGOs, academia, citizens engaged in the participatory activities	Short article/Press release Social media posts Direct email invitations Local/regional media Use of partners channels
Final Conference M36	To present project activities, results, outcomes and impact to a wider audience, increase the visibility of the project, connect with other RRI actors, dissemination of the results with the view to further exploitation to maximise the impact. To present benefits of territorial RRI and citizen engagement illustrated at examples of TRANSFORM regions as good practices, and also giving space to other projects/initiatives to inspire other regions to implement RRI	Policy makers, public authorities RRI practitioners (CSOs, NGOs, academia, research, networks and other relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives)	Website + website news Press release Social media campaign Direct email invitations Live Tweeting Use of partners channels, and multiplier to maximise outreach

	in their regional R&I ecosystems.		
TRANSFORM-organised sessions/events at third party events	To present project activities, disseminate the results of the project, build synergies and partnerships with other actors and show the impact of TRANSFORM at regional R&I policy.	Policy makers, public authorities RRI practitioners (CSOs, NGOs, academia, research, networks and other relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives)	Website + website news Social media Use of partners channels, and multiplier to maximise outreach

Local final events

Each regional cluster organised a final local event to present the implemented activities, results, outcomes and their impact at the local/regional level and engage local stakeholders. The events targeted wider communities created around the regional clusters and actors who took part in the activities, including policy makers, public authorities, CSOs, NGOs, Think Tank members, academia and research institutes, private sector representatives and local/regional companies, and public. Local final events were also an opportunity to celebrate the successful implementation of the project, future plans and aspiration and establish and strengthen community building and public engagement.

Lombardy final event

Title of the event: *Progetto TRANSFORM Evento finale locale*

La voce dei cittadini nelle politiche regionali di Ricerca e Innovazione

Date & time: 17 November 2022; 14:30 – 17:30

Location: Milan, Palazzo Pirelli (Sala Pirelli) - Lombardy Region

Agenda:

Italian version: <https://www.openinnovation.regione.lombardia.it/it/news/news/6917/la-voce-dei-cittadini-nel-policy-making-regionale-di-ricerca-e-innovaz>

English version:

Opening session

- **Welcome** by Fabrizio Sala, Vice-President and Councilor for Education, University, Research, Innovation and Simplification of [Lombardy Region](#)
- **Introduction to the day's theme** by Piero Bassetti, president of [Fondazione Giannino Bassetti](#) and *first Lombardy Region Governor*
- **Overview of the TRANSFORM project** by Angela Simone, TRANSFORM coordinator, [Fondazione Giannino Bassetti](#)

- *Region's perspective on the importance of integrating the voices of citizens in regional research and innovation policies* by Elisabetta Confalonieri and Enza Cristofaro, [Directorate General for Education, Universities, Research, Innovation and Simplification](#)

Participatory research agenda setting

- *Defining the regional strategic research and innovation agenda in a participatory way:* the first set of participatory activities focused on the theme of the just energy transition by Anna Pellizzone, TRANSFORM project manager, [Fondazione Giannino Bassetti](#)
- *How to integrate citizens' ideas and needs into regional strategies: Lombardy's Three-Year Strategic Program for Research, Innovation and Technology Transfer* by Silvia Corbetta, [Finlombarda](#)
- *Key note speech: "Just Ecological Transition for All. The role of citizens and society"* by Enrico Giovannini, Professor at [the University of Rome "Tor Vergata"](#)

TRANSFORM Citizen Jury

- *Results of the TRANSFORM Citizens Jury dedicated to responsible smart mobility* by Anna Pellizzone, [Fondazione Giannino Bassetti](#)
- *Integration of citizens' recommendations into smart mobility policies* in the Lombardy Region by Matteo Pozzetti, Directorate General for Education, Universities, Research, Innovation and Simplification, [Lombardy Region](#)
- *Key note: Role that citizens can play – reflection on accountability issues related to data-driven services, including aspects of privacy and data protection* (some of the elements considered most important by TRANSFORM's Citizens' Jury participants) by Guido Scorza, a member of [the Garante per la Protezione dei Dati Personali](#)

Discussion and closing remarks

- *TRANSFORM results and citizen participation in Research and Innovation decision-making* by Agnes Allansdottir, [University of Siena](#), a scholar of the relationship between science and society and an expert in methodologies for consulting citizens and monitoring public opinion on the impact of technologies and technosciences, chosen by the Region as one of the ten components of the Regional Forum for Innovation and Scientific Research 2018-2021

- **Closing remarks** by Angela Simone, TRANSFORM coordinator, [Fondazione Giannino Bassetti](#)

Number of participants: 125 (in presence and online - webstreaming)

Type of participants: policymakers and regional units' managers from Lombardy Region and other Italian Regions (i.e., Emilia-Romagna region), researchers (i.e., JRC, Politecnico of Milan, University of Bologna, etc.), innovators, private sector, associations and third sector's organisations, intermediaries (Chambre of Commerce, Confederation of Cooperatives, trade unions, etc.) representatives, citizens engaged in deliberative activities. Also, the Italian Representative of the Horizon Europe Missions Sub-group "Climate-neutral and Smart cities" was present.

Summary

On November 17th 2022, Lombardy Region hosted the final local event of TRANSFORM Lombardy cluster, co-organised with Fondazione Giannino Bassetti, with the support of Finlombarda. The final local event of the Lombardy cluster was a key step to ensure the transparency and fairness of the deliberative actions implemented and publicly sharing TRANSFORM results with different regional actors. 125 people took part in the conference, both in person and online.

The event engaged as speakers all TRANSFORM partners from the Lombardy cluster, as well as external keynote speakers and discussants (National Data Protection Authority spokesperson and former National Sustainable Mobility Minister).

The event successfully reached multiple objectives. First, the event was in itself a key step of the deliberative process, to ensure that the citizens engaged in the activities had the chance to learn how their recommendations were included in Lombardy Region policies.

The event was also relevant to share with regional policymakers the process and the outcomes of TRANSFORM in Lombardy, contributing to the diffusion of deliberative processes in the Region (and beyond, since also representatives from other Italian regions were present and also public authorities at the national level).

Furthermore, during the event, the role of citizens in R&I governance was also discussed within the two specific realms at the center of TRANSFORM activities: 1) just energy transition

for all (discussed in the deliberative workshop of TRANSFORM) and 2) data protection (one of the responsibility issues raised by citizens during the Citizens' Jury on Responsible Smart Mobility).

Regional R&I stakeholders from academia and industries also took part in the event, learning about public deliberation for policymaking and the advantages of engaging citizens in R&I governance.

The event was pivotal for the exploitation activities of the Lombardy cluster actions. Emilia-Romagna region got interested in concrete deliberative processes and, after the event, negotiated with FGB a training course based on TRANSFORM Lombardy processes and results that will be held from December 2022 to January 2023 in person in Bologna and online.

Full article: <https://www.transform-project.eu/lombardy-results-final-event/>

Brussels-Capital final event

Title of the event: Évènement de clôture projet TRANSFORM/Slotevenement van het project TRANSFORM (Closing event TRANSFORM project)

Date & time: 10 November 2022; 11:00 – 16:30

Location: Innoviris, 112 Chaussée de Charleroi, 1060 Saint-Gilles

Participants: 20

Type of participants: policy makers, civil society organisations, private sector

Agenda

Time	Session	Speakers
11 :00-11 :05	Welcome	Yannik Hallet – Cabinet Trachte
11:05-11:45	Introduction	Marzia Mazzonetto, BE participation ASBL

	<i>Presentation of TRANSFORM project and its activities in the Brussels-Capital region</i>	Ignace Adant, UCLouvain , Earth and Life Institute
11:45-11:50	Ice-breaker	Maite Debry, BE participation asbl
11:50-12:30	Recommendations and future perspectives The impacts of TRANSFORM project activities on citizen engagement practices in the governance of regional research and innovation	Marzia Mazzonetto, BE participation asbl Jeremy Levin, Innoviris
12:30-13:30	<i>Lunch</i>	
13:30-14:20	Roundtable on Responsible Research and Innovation Reflections on the RRI approach proposed by TRANSFORM, its potential applications, and the perspectives it opens up for public action in terms of Responsible Research & Innovation	Cassio Lopes – Perspectives Brussels Hamza Belakbir – Cabinet Maron
14:20-15:15	Participative session	Fabien Lambert and Maite Debry, BE participation asbl
15:15-15:45	<i>Coffee break</i>	
15:45-16:15	Inspirational speaker	Alain Boribon, Co-founder of Citizenfund & RECYCLO.coop (Unsold food pilot)
16:15-16:30	Closing	Jeremy Levin, Innoviris

Summary

On 10 November 2022, [Innoviris](#) (the regional institute for research and innovation), [BE participation asbl](#) (la Plateforme belge pour la participation citoyenne) and [UCLouvain](#) hosted the final regional event gathering twenty policymakers, civil society, and private sector representatives. The aim was to showcase the results, lessons learned and added value of the multi-stakeholder engagement activities. Presentations focused in particular on lessons

learnt from the three regional pilots, where multi-stakeholder engagement activities were implemented around two innovations (AquaSens, water sensors measuring water quality, and Algorella, an innovative food rich in vitamin B12), as well as an entire ecosystem where new bottom-up (social) innovations are blooming, that of the management of [unsold food](#)). These pilots have allowed Innoviris to experiment and familiarise itself with multi-stakeholder engagement at different stages of innovation governance, with a view in particular to its R&I governance.

At the level of regional public actors, the project in general and the discussions during the event have had the impact of leading to numerous reflections on the timing and use of citizen participation dynamics. Innoviris is now thinking about adapting its theme emergence process to include citizen participation.

Catalonia final event

Title of the event:

Recerca i innovació responsables, ciència ciutadana i polítiques públiques: aprenentatges del projecte TRANSFORM

Date & time: 21 November de 2022; 9:45 – 16:15

Location: Palau Robert, Barcelona

Agenda

Catalan version: <https://fonseuropeus.gencat.cat/ca/detalls/noticia/acte-final-transform>

English version:

- | | |
|---------------|--|
| 9:45 - 10:00 | Accreditations |
| 10:00 - 10:15 | Institutional welcome |
| 10:15 - 10:45 | "Citizen science: concept and transformative potential" <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Josep Perelló, professor at the University of Barcelona and leader of the OpenSystems group |
| 10:45 - 11:15 | "Citizen science as a tool for improving public policies: examples of success" <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Rosa Arias, founder and manager of Science for Change |
| 11:15 - 11:45 | Break |
| 11:45 - 12:30 | "Citizen science for the improvement of health care: the project on endometriosis in the first person at the Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau" |

- Elisa Llurba, director of the Obstetrics and Gynecology Service at the Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau
- Ramon Rovira, coordinator of the Surgical Area, the Gynecology Oncology Area and the Endometriosis Unit of the Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau
- Marta Fonseca, participant in the project
- Noelia Pitarque, participant in the project

Moderator: Nora Salas Seoane, Science for Change

12:30 - 13:15 **"Citizen science applied to local policies: the case of Mollet City Council and the selective collection of waste"**

- Myra Ronzoni, operational manager of the ECIU University project at the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
- Guifré Ortiz, head of the Urban Services Section of Mollet del Vallès City Council
- Sandra Palma, manager of the Municipal Institute of Education in Mollet del Vallès
- Adrià Navarro, student at Escola Sant Gervasi

Moderator: Diana Reinoso Botsho, Science for Change

13:15 - 14:30 **Lunch**

14:30 - 14:50 **"Citizen science in the framework of RIS3CAT 2030"**

- Tatiana Fernández, head of the Economic Strategy Area of the Secretariat of Economic Affairs and European Funds of the Department of Economy and Finance of the Generalitat of Catalonia

14:50 - 15:50 **Round table "Challenges and opportunities of citizen science in Catalonia"**

- Xavier Gironès, coordinator of Territorial Impact of Knowledge of the Department of Research and Universities of the Generalitat de Catalunya
- Xavier Ariño, head of the Institutional Projects Office of the Autonomous University of Barcelona
- Diana Escobar, project coordinator of the Department of Science and Universities of Barcelona City Council
- Ignasi Labastida, delegate of the chancellor in open science at the University of Barcelona

Moderator: Sergio Martínez, Secretary of Economic Affairs and European Funds of the Department of Economy and Finance of the Generalitat of Catalonia

15.50 - 16.15 **Closing**

Number of participants: 70

Type of participants: policy makers; regional and local public authorities, academia, research, companies

Summary

On November 21, the Catalan cluster of the TRANSFORM project held its final event to share the results and lessons learned acquired during these 3 years of work. Under the title "Responsible research and innovation, citizen science and public policies" more than 70 people attended the event held at the Palau Robert.

The event began with a welcome and presentations by Dr Josep Perelló, leader of the OpenSystems group, and Rosa Arias, CEO of Science for Change. During their presentations, both underlined **the importance and transformative potential of citizen science as a tool to improve public policies**. This introduction was followed by the round table presentations of two citizen science pilots – on waste and health (endometriosis) that have been carried out in the Catalan territory with representatives of each pilot including project partners and local partners who took part in the pilots.

To close the event, Tatiana Fernández, Head of the Economic Strategy Area of the Secretariat for Economic Affairs and European Funds of the Generalitat de Catalunya, shared with the attendees the role of citizen science within the framework of RIS3CAT 2030 and also its experience and learning from the TRANSFORM project. The participants discussed the challenges and opportunities of citizen science in Catalonia in a round table session. Some of the key points that were discussed in this round table were: the need to establish a return to citizenship, have platforms or agents that act as a link between the different actors involved, the need to create spaces for innovation around the territory and generate a relationship of trust between the agents involved in citizen science projects.

Full article: <https://www.transform-project.eu/wp-admin/post.php?post=4478&action=elementor>

Final conference

Title: TRANSFORMing the territorial R&I governance. RRI and citizen engagement to open up regional R&I policymaking.

Format: Hybrid

Date & place: 1 – 2 December, Milan (Italy) + online (Zoom)

The consortium has opted for a hybrid event with an in-person conference at the Museo Nazionale della Scienza e della Tecnologia Leonardo da Vinci in Milan, Italy, and an online event that remote participants could follow via Zoom as suggested by TRANSFORM's Project Officer.

The TRANSFORM Final Conference aimed to create a space for sharing and knowledge among key stakeholders. The target audience was RRI enablers and practitioners across Europe, with a particular focus on regional public authorities, policymakers, NGOs, CSOs, the private sector, and academia working on and/or interested in territorial RRI and citizen engagement to further raise awareness about the topics, challenges and opportunities, disseminate the project results and outcomes, foster their uptake and maximise the impact.

Objectives

The main objectives of the TRANSFORM Final Conference were to:

- Provide a synthesis of the main policy and practice-oriented findings of the project.
- Present project activities results and outcomes to further disseminate the project results and outcomes and to foster the exploitation of results.
- Launch Strategic Roadmaps for the implementation and support of territorial RRI through three methodologies - Participatory Research Agenda Setting, Multi-stakeholder Engagement and Citizen Science - developed by each cluster and project e-book.
- Bring together territorial RRI stakeholders to learn, share and network, presenting not only TRANSFORM as an inspirational case but also presenting CC-PES project and the mutual learning between TRANSFORM partners and our overseas partner Museum of Boston and other relevant projects, initiatives, and EU practices of citizen and stakeholder engagement in R&I processes and policies.
- Increase the visibility of the project.

Participation

Overall, 82 people registered for the event (both days). Due to Zoom technical problems potentially more people could have been registered (the full list of registrants on Monday and Tuesday before the final event has been erased by the system). The conference had 61 participants in total for the two days, both online and onsite. The participants represented public authorities and policymakers at various levels including representatives of EU

institutions (DG REGIO, JRC), managing and regional authorities, but also research and academia, EU networks (ERRIN, Eurocities), private sector, NGOs and CSOs.

Agenda & Speakers

Full agenda: <https://www.transform-project.eu/final-conference-2022/>

The agenda for the two-day event was prepared by FGB in cooperation with project partners. It was designed to give space to present the activities, results and outcomes of three regional clusters presented by all involved project partners and AB members, and give space to key EU initiatives, with speakers from various backgrounds working on different topics in relation to territorial RRI, deliberation and citizen engagement.

The legacy of the TRANSFORM project was presented at two levels – by regional clusters and the long-term impact of TRANSFORM activities at regional level by incorporating the results and lessons learned in strategic policies, programmes, R&I governance and internal processes. Key tools to inspire further territories were launched during the conference – The executive summary of the ‘Strategic roadmap for the implementation and support of territorial RRI through participatory research agenda setting /multi-stakeholder engagement/citizen science within S3 priorities’ and project e-book.

The event brought together 25 speakers (– internal (project partners and AB members) and external speakers) from across Europe presenting various stakeholders (public authorities and policymakers at various levels from EU to local; academia, private sectors, NGOs and CSOs, EU networks).

A poster session was held during the two days of the Final Conference, giving a chance to relevant projects and initiatives working on RRI and citizen engagement topics to share their work, boost their visibility, and meet and exchange with RRI practitioners from across Europe. Five projects were selected to prepare posters, displayed and presented during the Final Conference: [MOSAIC](#); [BRIDGES – Building Reflexivity and response-ability Involving Different narratives of knowledGES](#); [ENJOI \(ENGagement and JOurnalism Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication\)](#); Participatory initiatives for transforming and developing the Italian mountains in a sustainable way.

Communication

The planning of the communication campaign for the final event started in July 2022 with the implementation from August to December 2022. While FGB was in charge of the overall organisation of the event, AEIDL was responsible for the communication of the final conference, building the communication strategy, creating the visual identity, communication and promotional materials and dissemination channels of the conference. Below you can find a table with the main actions identified with the strategy.

The following elements were part of the communication of the event:

- **Visual identity** created for the Final Conference in line with the overall TRANSFORM visual identity.
- The [website](#) for the final conference – embedded in the project’s official website providing essential information about the conference logically structured into Home Page, Agenda, Call for posters and Practical information.
- **E-mail invitations** sent to personalised direct mailing targeted more than 250 relevant contacts, targeting RRI practitioners.
- **Social media channels** of the project were one of the main channels to promote the final conference. Twitter and LinkedIn were deployed with key messages, attractive visuals and a video trailer to invite people to the conference. Direct messages on Twitter were sent to 41 relevant projects dealing with topics related to territorial RRI and citizen engagement in R&I. Twitter was used to live-tweet relevant quotes and key information during the conference.
- A **promotional kit** (banners, social media visuals, text for social media posts, short web article) was developed by AEIDL to 1) facilitate the communication efforts of the partners; 2) guide partners in communicating about the final conference; 3) ensure consistency in the overall communication activities.
- **Promotional event material** (roll-up, badges, online cards) was developed by a graphic designer for the event.
- **Channels of the project partners** acting as multipliers to widen the outreach.

Communication outcomes of the conference

[The news article](#) about the conference and its outcomes were published on the TRANSFORM website in English on 21 December.

A direct personalised mailing was sent to inform the target audience about the outcomes of the conference and to further disseminate project results (Executive Summaries of the Strategic Roadmaps, Project e-book and videos) to over 200 contacts.

[An additional project video](#) was shot during the conference, giving space to project partners to present their TRANSFORMative journey, activities, benefits and impact. The objective was to

promote territorial RRI and citizen engagement in (regional) R&I policy and governance to create policies more aligned with citizens' needs, values and aspirations.

More details about the Final Conference can be found in the D6.6 Final event report submitted in M36.

TRANSFORM-organised events within third-party events and initiatives

In addition, project partners investigated possibilities to organise sessions within the framework of the umbrella events covering relevant topics (R&I, citizen engagement, circular economy, green transition, etc.) to reach a wider public and to communicate about the project, its activities and disseminate the results. AEIDL coordinated the organisation of the event-related activities. Five events/sessions were organised within the framework of third-party events by TRANSFORM.

- [Citizen engagement TRANSFORMing regional R&I policymaking](#) in the framework of the EU Week of Regions and Cities

TRANSFORM was selected to organise the session during the European Week of Regions and Cities 2021. The participatory lab session '[Citizen engagement TRANSFORMing regional R&I policymaking - 12PL21711](#)' presented activities, preliminary results and lessons learned of three regional clusters in an interactive participatory way. The session took place on **12 October 2021**. 117 participants registered, and 32 participated. TRANSFORM partners took part in the promotional activities organised by DG REGIO and the CoR. Angela Simone, TRANSFORM Project Coordinator, took part in the coffee with partners and the promotional video produced for this thematic strand. Moreover, AEIDL prepared a social media campaign to boost the participation and created an infographic summarising the outcomes of the event.

- ["TRANSFORM. Giving citizens a seat at the table of R&I regional policymaking. The Lombardy region case"](#) at the *TeRRItoria's #ResponsibleRegions*

On **16 December 2021**, Angela Simone, TRANSFORM project coordinator and leader of the Lombardy regional cluster, presented Lombardy's experience and approach to integrating citizen engagement activities into regional R&I governance, the results of which have been incorporated into the 2021-2023 Strategic Programme for Research and Innovation. #ResponsibleRegions is a series of monthly webinars dealing with the concepts of the Smart

Specialisation Strategy (S3) and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). [EURADA](#) and the [TeRRItoria](#) consortium are organising these webinars with the aim of sharing the valuable experience of Regional Development Agencies (RDAs) and local actors in developing and adapting strategies for regional development. The recording of the session is available [here](#).

- **Launch event of the Italian translation of the [“Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions: Catching the Deliberative Wave”](#) report**

FGB engaged in a cooperation with OECD – Open Government, Civic Space and Public Communication Unit and the OECD during the summer and autumn of 2021, on the development of the Italian translation of the Highlights 2020 of the OECD report [“Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions: Catching the Deliberative Wave”](#), and organisation of a [launch event](#) to present it. The launch event took place on **25 October 2021** (online) in cooperation with OECD, JRC Ispra, National Commission for Public Debate – Italian Ministry of Sustainable Infrastructure and Mobility (Italy), Lombardy Region, Directorate General for Education, University, Research, Innovation and Simplification, and Emilia-Romagna Region, General Directorate for the Economy of Knowledge, Labour and Business Communication channels and tools. The Italian translation of the report is available (open access) on the TRANSFORM website and Open Innovation (Lombardy) website. It aims to provide Italian policy makers and interested stakeholders with an instrument to navigate opportunities, methodologies, and best practices of citizen engagement and deliberation.

- [Citizens’ voices for regional R&I agendas: the TRANSFORM experience](#)
a workshop organised at the EUSEA22 Let’s Co-Create the Future

On **6 June 2022**, TRANSFORM organised a session in which three regional clusters represented by Anna Pellizzone (Lombardy), Diana Reinoso (Catalonia) and Maite Debry (Brussels-Capital) shared their experiences and lessons learned. By sharing knowledge and showcasing promising outcomes, this session provided examples of how quadruple helix stakeholders can work together to create a more open, transparent and inclusive regional R&I governance. #EUSEA22. “Co-Creating the Future” (organised in Cork, Ireland) discussed the power of collaborations, explore the magic of stakeholder engagement and reflect the challenges of co-creation. The full 2-day programme offered an inspiring and interactive programme with 22 horizon talks, 15 sessions and 2 keynotes. 39 speakers presented their visions and examples of co-creating the future.

- [First-person experiences of endometriosis. Participatory research, needs and recommendations of people with endometriosis.](#)
a joint webinar TRANSFORM-FEMale project

On 13 October 2022, TRANSFORM (Science for Change) and the FEMale project organised a joint webinar. TRANSFORM's Catalan cluster leads a [citizen science pilot project on endometriosis](#) with the aim of involving the patient and co-creating recommendations for the improvement of healthcare services. In this webinar, Diana Reinoso and Nora Salas Seoane from [Science of Change](#) presented the methodology, co-creation and participatory activities involving patients, as well as the challenges encountered and how they overcame them. The research results were presented along with recommendations for improving healthcare services for people suffering from endometriosis and influencing policy.

The webinar was led by Ulrik Bak Kirk, [FEMaLe](#) Project Coordinator.

Third party events

Throughout the duration of the project, TRANSFORM partners continuously identified opportunities to actively participate in external events (conferences, workshops, etc.), targeting relevant domains for the project, to present the project, boost its visibility and disseminate results and increases the project visibility. The impact of participation at this kind of event is very high because of the attendance of representatives of public authorities and policy makers. Workshops, meetings and other regional and EU events represent relevant and important opportunities for dissemination.

A list below provides an overview of dissemination events attended by project partners.:

12 events within M1 – M15

- [Pint of Science Festival in Brussels: 'Shaping the city of tomorrow'](#), 7-10 September 2020
Organised by Pint of Science in partnership with Innoviris, the TRANSFORM project and BE Participation, the event first introduced the latest research on how cities can adapt to the environment and socio-economic challenges, while working better for and with citizens. TRANSFORM was presented on stage, and an interactive session moderated by BE participation allowed citizens to share their ideas on how to make Brussels city greener as part of a European Union-wide public consultation. The event was attended by state-secretary Barbara Trachte. The event had around 30 participants.
- [Ricerca, innovazione e bene comune webinar](#) organised by Art-ER, 25 September 2020
FGB presented TRANSFORM and the citizen engagement methodologies explored in the project during the webinar organised by Art-ER, one of the partners in the TeRRItoria project. The event was held in Italian as it was devoted to Italian stakeholders only, with around 100 participants.

- [European Week of Regions 2020, 'Shared agendas beyond EDP'](#), 7 October 2020
In the session dedicated to S3, EDP and citizen engagement, GENCAT presented “Coalitions for transformative change through shared agendas in Catalonia”.
- On **17th November 2021**, FGB presented TRANSFORM in an online [workshop on science communication and citizen engagement](#) addressed to [Fondazione Cariplo](#) grantees.
- [3rd Citizen Engagement and Deliberative Democracy Festival, 6-12 December 2020](#)
TRANSFORM's project video was selected for the virtual exhibition of citizen engagement projects available during the whole week of the Festival.
- [Research as a driving force for change in public policy: series of sessions on the interaction between politics and science and on collaborative research, 4-18 February 2021](#). During the month of February, [the School of Public Administration of Catalonia \(EAPC\)](#) offered a series of sessions on the interaction between politics and science and on collaborative research. In the session "Collaborative research. How do we move from theory to practice? Methodologies, experiences and lessons learned" on 18 February, SfC presented TRANSFORM and the citizen science methodology. This series of sessions was aimed at policy officers from Catalonia. Over 100 participants attended this specific session.
- UiB presented the TRANSFORM approach to RRI monitoring and evaluation at a [project webinar of MARIE](#) in February 2021.
- The TRANSFORM approach has been presented in webinars and courses in the Norwegian university sector, including the two national R&I centers called the [Centre for Digital Life Norway](#) and the [AFINO Centre for RRI](#), and a joint workshop with [Nord University](#) and [the University of Agder](#), for a total of approx. 60 participants; as well as in a webinar with the Austrian network for RRI, with approx. 15 participants from research organisations.
- On **3rd March 2021**, FGB presented TRANSFORM in a [workshop on RRI](#) at Politecnico of Milan addressed to alumni and researchers and grantees of the initiative [Get it! Twice](#), promoted by [Fondazione Social Venture Giordano Bruno Dall'Amore](#).
- On the 25th March 2021, BE participation presented TRANSFORM and activities of the Brussels-Capital regional cluster during the workshop about the socio-ecological transition run by [POSECO](#). Around 15 participants, representing regional R&I actors, attended the webinar.

35 events within M16 – M36

- AEIDL prepared a **project poster** which was presented by FGB during the [NewHoRRizon conference](#) (online) on 20 May 2021, presenting TRANSFORM's activities, objectives, preliminary results and lessons learned.
- On 10 June 2021, SfC presented **TRANSFORM poster** at the [9a Trobada de Gestors: RRI With & For Research Managers. Get set for Horizon Europe](#) targeting policy makers. The event was co-organised with the Centre de Regulació Genòmica (CRG), the Institut Hospital del Mar d'Investigacions Mèdiques (IMIM), the Institut de Salut Global de Barcelona (ISGlobal) and the Universitat Pompeu Fabra (UPF) and with the support of the GRACE project.

- FGB and SfC gave an **oral presentation** of the TRANSFORM, presenting co-creation and participative methodologies applied within the project and talking about RRI in regional programming from a perspective of Catalonia, one of the pioneers in the implementation of RRI in the regional R&I, during the [TeRRitoria webinar by ARTe](#) (Italian stakeholders). The webinar took place on 16 June 2021.
- GENCAT presented TRANSFORM to the scientific community during the **Workshop on citizen Science at Universtitat Autònoma de Barcelona** on 22 June 2021.
- During the [European Research and Innovation days](#) (23-24 June 2021), **TRANSFORM video** was presented in the video gallery at the [JRC House](#) within the Horizon Village, in the corner with the External links, following 'the Spotlight on JRC: the European Commission's science and knowledge service'.
- BEpart presented TRANSFORM during the **Cluster event: Institutional changes towards open science and societal engagement in research and innovation (REA)** on 1 July 2021.
- **A poster** jointly prepared by SfC and AEIDL was submitted and featured during the [Catalonia Researchers Night 2021](#) (21 September 2021, posters still available online) focusing on Catalan cluster and activities. The event is popularising science, research and innovation among the general public.
- On 29 September 2021, GENCAT and SFC took part in the **workshop 'Policy masterclass citizen science in sustainability transitions: why and how?'** in Barcelona, **presenting TRANSFORM** activities and results to policy makers and practitioners. The event was organised within the framework of ACTION project.
- Several partners took part in "[SeeRRI Final Conference "Bringing RRI into regional planning: From theory to SeeRRI"](#) held in Barcelona on 29 - 30 September 2021, and related activities. Angela Simone (FGB) took part in a session 'Impact of cross-project collaboration'. together with Nhien Nguyen ([SeeRRI](#) Project Coordinator) and Marianne Hörlesberger ([DigiTeRRI](#) Project Coordinator). On the second day, Marzia Mazzonetti (BE participation), took part in a session 'How mutual learning happens between regions in EU projects' together with Elisabetta Marinelli (Advisory Board member in [SeeRRI](#)) and Tanja Adnađević ([TeRRIFICA project](#)). Moreover, AEIDL prepared a poster which was presented by TRANSFORM partners during the conference and together with FGB, prepared a contribution on behalf of TRANSFORM to the [SeeRRI booklet](#).
- FGB presented territorial approach to RRI and citizen engagement activities of TRANSFORM during the hybrid event "[La roadmap lombarda per la transizione ecologica](#)" on 1 October 2020.
- On 20 October 2021, SfC gave an **oral presentation** during the workshop [Sesión clínica "Experiencia de paciente"](#) in Barcelona presenting health pilot to regional policy makers and scientific community.
- FGB gave **oral presentation** on TRANSFORM during the training [Intensive School in Science Communicatio Pavia University](#) on 18 November 2021, and during the **Online Workshop with Lombardy Region policy makers** on 19 November 2021.
- FGB presented TRANSFORM during the **OECD's virtual conference on Technology in and for Society: Innovating well for inclusive transitions** on 6 December 2021, targeting international and European stakeholders.

- TRANSFORM partners took part in the [GRACE Final Webinar series](#). BEpart presented TRANSFORM in a session '[Making the case for public engagement](#)' on 2 November 2021, while SfC presented TRANSFORM experience in Catalonia in the session [on Public Engagement: The research funders' perspective](#) on 16 November 2021.
- FGB presented TRANSFORM during the TeRRItoria's Final Conference, in the session [How to engage citizens in regional development policies](#) on 18 January 2022 targeting stakeholders at European level.
- On 26 March 2022, SfC and UB took part in the [EndoMarch 2022](#) in Barcelona, presenting health pilot to regional stakeholders.
- UCLouvain presented TRANSFORM pilot of Brussels-Capital region during the [Water Symposium RESCIF](#) at Louvain-la-Neuve and online. The event took place on 31 March 2022 targeting scientific community.
- On 8 April 2022, FGB **presented** TRANSFORM project during **the Lessons at Politecnico di Milano (Executive Master on the Management of Research, Innovation and Technology)** in Milan targeting policy makers at national level.
- UiB **co-authored an abstract** selected for the presentation during the [REvaluation Conference 2021](#) in Vienna. The event targeting scientific community took place on 5 and 6 May 2022.
- On 10 May 2022, SfC gave an **oral presentation** of TRANSFORM focusing on health pilot activities during the training [Avaluació de l'experiència de pacients: primers passos](#) in Barcelona, targeting health professionals.
- SfC in cooperation with AEIDL submitted and presented **posters** in two sessions presenting the health and the waste pilots of Catalonia during the [C*sci Conference](#). The conference was organised online from 23 to 26 May 2022.
- On 4 June 2022, BEpart and FGB **co-organised the panel** [Citizen engagement remastered](#) at the ECSITE conference in Heilbronn (Germany), presenting TRANSFORM.
- **A joint poster** coordinated by AEIDL was presented by FGB with [ENJOI project](#) and [MOSAIC project](#) at the [ESOF conference](#) (13 – 16 July 2022) in Leiden.
- SfC, UiB and BEpart took part in **different seasons as speakers**, presenting different aspects of TRANSFORM, from experiences to activities and approach during the [EASST 2022 – THE POLITICS OF TECHNOLOGICAL FUTURES](#) in Madrid (6-8 June 2022).
- FGB gave an oral presentation at the online meeting organized by EURADA, '[EU H2020 POCITYF project 6th Smart Heritage Cities Working Group](#)', on 9 June 2022, targeting policy makers at all levels.
- UiB presented a paper Transformative Translations? at the [Eu-SPRI 2022 - Challenging Science and Innovation Policy](#), within the Transformative innovation policy and RRI topic. The conference took place in Utrecht (the Netherlands) on 1 July 2022.
- SfC took part in the [ECSA Conference 2022](#) in Berlin, organised from 5 to 8 October 2022, targeting the scientific community at EU level. TRANSFORM waste pilot of Catalonia was presented during the **participatory workshop** and the **joint poster** TRANSFORM-FEMale project was presented focusing on the health pilot.

- FGB presented the **Citizens Jury and its outcomes** at the ["Abitare il domani" - Convegno nazionale di Future Studies](#) in Naples on 15 October 2022 to the national scientific community.
- SfC took part in the [X-Patient Congress 2022](#) in Barcelona on 28 and 29 September 2022. **The health pilot** of Catalonia was presented and considered as **one of the best 5 projects presented**. The event targets scientific community and health professionals at national level.
- BEpart **presented TRANSFORM** activities at the [ECREA 2022 9th European Communication Conference](#) in Aarhus, which took place from 19 to 22 October 2022.
- GENCAT presented TRANSFORM during the [RRI Leaders Policy Learning Workshop: The transformative potential of responsible research and innovation in territorial policymaking](#) in Sabadell (Spain). The event targeted policy makers at EU level. It took place on 22 October 2022 within the framework of the **RRI Leaders project**.
- On 27 October 2022, SfC took part in the [CSC Impulsa Awards](#) in which health pilot of Catalonia **won the 2nd prize** including financial reward. On the same day, **UB presented health pilot** at the [Congreso AFIN Salut reproductiva](#) in Barcelona.
- [TRANSFORM video](#) was selected for the participation in the project exhibition during the [4th Public Participation and Deliberative Democracy Festival](#) organised by JRC (20 – 21 October 2022).

Cluster-specific communication and dissemination activities

Regional clusters also developed some specific communication, dissemination and outreach activities and products at the regional level to reach local citizens and stakeholders in national languages.

The objectives of regional communication, dissemination and outreach activities and products are:

- To inform local citizens and stakeholders about the project and its activities taking place at the regional level;
- To engage citizens and local stakeholder (CSOs, NGOs, academia and research institutes, policy makers and public authorities, companies and industry) in regional activities;
- To disseminate project results at the regional level;
- To raise overall visibility of the project, the local partners involved, its activities and outcomes at regional/local level;
- To ensure the transparency of the citizen' engagement processes conducted at the regional level;
- To provide participants directly engaged in TRANSFORM's participatory exercises with all the relevant information on the citizen' engagement process;
- To increase the awareness around key TRANSFORM issues (i.e. RRI, citizen engagement, responsible S3 design and implementation, etc.).

Each cluster decided to pursue different activities and products to reach these objectives.

Lombardy regional cluster

In addition to the local final event organised in November 2022, Lombardy region engaged in the following communication and dissemination efforts:

- [TRANSFORM animation](#) and [second project video](#) available with Italian subtitles.
- **Production of multimedia material:**
 - Public reports of the participatory activities conducted online and in person ([Citizens' Jury](#), [survey](#), [deliberative workshop](#)) both in English and in Italian
 - Pictures of the participatory activities conducted online and in person
 - Two videos of the participatory activities ([Citizens' Jury with shootings during the jury meetings; survey and deliberative workshop with scribing graphics technique](#)) in Italian and with subtitles in English
 - [Pictures](#) and [recordings](#) of the final local event
 - [The Italian translation](#) of the OECD report "Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions: Catching the Deliberative Wave – Highlights"
 - Executive Summary of the Strategic Roadmaps for the implementation and support of territorial RRI through Participatory Research Agenda Setting within S3 priorities (in [English](#) and in Italian)
- A [dedicated webpage](#) on **Open Innovation** to collect:
 - All the communication and multimedia material abovementioned, as well as general information on TRANSFORM project and Lombardy Cluster activities, participatory activities timeline, datasets, presentations of the speakers from the final local event
 - Continuous update (news)
- **Communication activities** to maximize the impact of the project through FGB's channels (news on the FGB website, FGB newsletter, FGB social media channels – Facebook, Twitter, Instagram - extensive mailing to FGB contacts), Lombardy Regions' channels (Open Innovation newsletter and social media – Facebook, Twitter) and Finlombarda's channels (mailing list, social media – LinkedIn).
- **Workshops** with Lombardy Region policymakers and R&I stakeholders (regional technological clusters) to share TRANSFORM process and results after each participatory action.
 - On the **6th and 8th of October 2020**, FGB actively took part to the [stakeholder meetings](#) as well as to [LR General Directorates meetings](#) planned by LR and Finlombarda for the design of S3, presenting TRANSFORM project and bringing RRI and citizen' engagement in the process.
 - During the **online workshop**, which took place on 24 September 2021, upon invitation **with Lombardy Region DDGG**, FGB presented the results of the TRANSFORM project actions in Lombardy, targeting policy makers.

- On 25 October 2022, FGB presented the Citizens' Jury results during the **workshop with Lombardy Region Directorates on TRANSFORM actions in Lombardy**, targeting policy makers at regional level.

Brussels-Capital regional cluster

In addition to the local final event organised in November, Lombardy region engaged in the following communication and dissemination efforts:

- TRANSFORM animation with [French](#) and [Dutch](#) subtitles and [second project video](#) available with French subtitles.
- **Extensive mailing** to representatives from Civil Society Organisations (non-profit organisations, associations) and other actors (academia and research institutes, policy makers and public authorities, companies and industry) to involve in cluster participatory activities and engage as multipliers to reach out a wider public;
- **Short video** presenting the participatory activities of the regional cluster with key actors concerned by the cluster pilot interviews;
- **Communication campaign** to reach out to citizens to engage in participatory activities, namely collective intelligence workshops to test circular economy innovations linked to the Brussels- Capital territory.
- Information provided on [BE participation website](#) about the TRANSFORM project, and the pilot activities coordinated by BE participation and use of BE participation social media channels.
- **Final report of the pilot on the flow of unsold food** ([FR](#) and [NL](#)) to communicate about the process and the results of this activity, sent out by emails and published on BE participation website.

Catalonia regional cluster

In addition to the local final event organised in November, Catalonia region engaged in the following communication and dissemination efforts:

- [TRANSFORM animation](#) and a [second project video](#) available with Catalan subtitles.
- **Think Tank webinars & meetings:** In 2020, the TRANSFORM [Catalan regional cluster](#) organised four webinars to foster knowledge exchange, open discussions and experimentations about RRI & citizen science. In this [series of participatory webinars](#), the TRANSFORM project was presented to the 55 Think Tank members - representatives from public administrations, research organisations and businesses of the Catalan R&I ecosystem. Two more webinars were conducted in 2021 to share with the Think Tank members the development and lessons learned during both citizen science pilots and to deepen the potentialities of citizen science for Shared Agendas. In 2022, the Think Tank members have been invited to the final local event to learn and reflect on the experiences of the different stakeholders engaged in the pilots and to collectively debate about the

potentialities of citizen science to align public policies to societal needs. In addition, Think Tank members have been regularly informed by e-mail about progress and outputs.

- **An open presentation of the health pilot** for all the women that showed interest in being part of the research, which took part on 13 May 2021 and lasted around 1,5 hours.
- **A simple brochure of the pilot on waste** was designed and sent to all the schools of Mollet de Valles to spark the interest, boost the involvement and provide information.
- Communication activities to maximize the impact of the project through SfC channels (website, social media), Gencat channels (website, social media) and UB channels (website, social media).
- **Public reports of the participatory activities** conducted in two pilots: [waste pilot](#) and [health pilot](#), both available in English and Catalan.
- On 12 December, the Catalan cluster [hold a meeting](#) with the acting president of the Catalan Parliament Ms. Alba Vergés Bosch (former health minister), Mr. José Rodríguez Fernández and Mr. Jordi Albert i Caballero - deputies of the Parliamentary Group Esquerra Republicana de Catalunya) to present the research results and to call for greater efforts by the political structures to improve the health care received by endometriosis patients.
- SfC is preparing **an article** with a tentative title "*First-person experiences of endometriosis in Catalonia: recommendations of women with endometriosis for improving health care services and public policies.*" Which will be published in first quarter of 2023 in Frontiers.
- **Videos** presenting waste and health pilot projects.

Communication and Dissemination products

Table 6 provides a summary of dissemination products developed within the project, including a short description, detailing target audience(s) and dissemination channels deployed for each product. Please note that the consortium was instructed to only publish and disseminate the deliverables approved by the REA, therefore some of these deliverables will be published after the project is completed. All these results will stay available after the project duration on the project website (for 2 years), Zenodo and channels of project partners.

Table 5: Communication and dissemination products overview

Product	Description	Target audience	Channels
Promo materials	Brochures, leaflets, infographics, etc.	Citizens, CSOs, NGOs Local authorities Academia & Research Industry & Companies Media	Social media Website Events Partners channels
Audio-visual material (videos, images)	Videos (animation, final video, additional videos about regional activities, video from the final conference, capacity building sessions recording) and photo galleries from project meetings and final conference.	Citizens, CSOs, NGOs Local authorities Academia & Research Industry & Companies Media	Social media Website Events EC channels Partners channels
Project e-book	An e -book presents the experimentation processes of all three clusters explored in the project, detailing used methodologies, strengths, weaknesses and practical hints to replicate the activities; an easy-to-use guide for policymakers and local stakeholders to implement RRI and participatory approaches in S3.	Local authorities CSOs, NGOs Academia & Research Industry & Companies Media	Social media Website Direct mailing Zenodo Partners channels
Reports on activities from regional clusters	<p>Brussels: Unsold food pilot report (FR & NL)</p> <p>Lombardy: Report on the survey and deliberative workshop (EN & IT) Report on the Citizen’s Jury on Responsible Smart Mobility (EN & IT)</p> <p>Catalonia: Report on waste pilot (EN & Catalan) Policy Brief: First-person experiences of endometriosis in Catalonia (EN & Catalan)</p>	Academia & Research Local authorities Related projects and initiatives	Website Social media Partners channels Zenodo
Strategic Roadmaps of the implementation of RRI in S3 through participatory research agenda/ citizen science/ design thinking for social innovations	<p>Executive summaries of the Strategic Roadmaps aim at helping regional public administrations who wish to enable citizens’ and R&I stakeholder engagement actions in their local policymaking. It presents the methodology, expected benefits, actions carried out, impact and lessons learned.</p> <p>Full deliverables (to be published after accepted by the REA)</p>	Local authorities CSOs, NGOs Academia & Research	<p>Website Social media Partners channels</p> <p>Website, Zenodo</p>

Policy Recommendations to transforming regional R&I systems towards RRI	Inspiring regional governments and local authorities which would like to replicate transformative processes and implement RRI components within their R&I policies.	Policy makers	Website Social media Partners channels Zenodo
Impact Pathways for RRI Initiatives in Regional R&I Ecosystem	A scientific publication that will disseminate the results from the assessment of scientific, environmental, economic and social impact pathways and benefits of TRANSFORM activities.	Academia & Research Local authorities Related projects and initiatives	Website Partners channels Zenodo
The TRANSFORM Monitoring and Evaluation Guide	A scientific publication that will disseminate the integrated results from monitoring and evaluation (WP7) of TRANSFORM.	Academia & Research Local authorities Related projects and initiatives	Website Social Media Partners channels Zenodo
TRANSFORM: An assessment of Outcomes and Impacts	A scientific publication providing final assessment of TRANSFORM activities; disseminate the final results of RRI assessment of the activities and outcomes of TRANSFORM together with other WP7 results.	Academia & Research Local authorities Related projects and initiatives	Website Social Media Partners channels Zenodo

Quality Control

Communication Team

The WP6 'Sharing results and multiplying impacts', led by AEIDL, required input and close cooperation with other work packages and project partners. The core communication team comprised of each WP representatives, and a wider communication team brings together one representative per partner.

Table 6: Communication team

Team member	Organisation	Role
Angela Simone	FGB	Project Coordinator
Lucia Princikova	AEIDL	WPL
Christopher Murnaghan	AEIDL	Animation
Thomas Chullikal	AEIDL	Web development
Robin Salter	AEIDL	Video edition
Prody Mwemena Julie de Galard	AEIDL	PR / Social Media
Angela Simone Anna Pellizzone	FGB	PCO, WP1, WP3 Lombardy cluster communication representatives
Marzia Mazzonetto Maité Debry	BEPart	WP2, WP5 Brussels cluster communication representatives
Diana Reinoso	SfC	WP4 Catalonia cluster communication representative
Kamilla Stølen	UiB	WP7 representative

Timeline

Table 7: WP6 Timeline

WP6: Sharing results and multiplying impacts																																							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36			
C&D Plan				D6.1											D6.4																							D6.7	
Visual Identity				D6.2			D6.3																																
Website				M12																																			
Social Media				M12																																			
Audio-visual material																																					M15	M15	
Dissemination events																																							
TRANSFORM events																																						M13	D6.6
eBook																																					D6.5	M14	

KPIs

Regular monitoring and evaluation activities were conducted to measure gains and successes and provide information about progress with implementation and help revisit and align the overall objectives. The evaluation of qualitative and quantitative performance data was used to:

- optimise the Plan and ongoing activities;
- correct and fine-tune planning;
- make targeting more effective and therefore increase reach;
- improve activities and products;
- improve efficiency and minimise costs.

Metrics and dimensions from offline tactics (e.g. the number of Conference attendees) and their online equivalents (e.g. shared content on social media, number of followers, etc.) were used to gather data to provide an analysis of KPIs from all related communication activities.

Data are being collected from the following sources:

- Web analytics tools
- Social media analytics tools
- Events

Table 9 below presents KPIs set at the beginning of the project and the achieved results in M36. Indicators of success inform progress towards achieving project objectives. The proposed KPIs below are guided by the European Commission (2015a) H2020 Programme indicators and aim to capture the achievements in communicating the project.

Table 8: Key Performance Indicators

	KPI	Targets (M36)	M36
Website	Number of unique visits on TRANSFORM website	5000	11 400+
Social media	No of Twitter followers	500	820
	No of LinkedIn group members	200	63
Videos	No of views	350 per video	1 st video: 464 2 nd video: 75 (only published in Nov 2022)
Press release	No of press releases issued	4	4
EC channels	Frequency of use of EU communication services	2-4/year	14 (Cordis, events, social media, promotional activities)
Webinar/Hybrid final conference	No of participants	30	35 registered 20 attended

Project e-book	Number of downloads	50	59
Local final events	No of participants	50	Lombardy: 125 Catalonia: 70 Brussels: 20 Total: 215
Final conference	No of participants	100	61
Events	No of presentations/active participation in third-party events	10+	47 + 9 TRANSFORM-organised events
Stakeholder engagement	No of quadruple helix stakeholders involved in local participatory activities	200+	Lombardy: 10 Catalonia: 90 Brussels: 80 Total: 180
Citizen outreach	No of citizens involved in local participatory activities	2000+	Lombardy: 1045 Catalonia: 500 Brussels: 130 Total: 1675
Policy makers reached	No of additional regional governments engaged	8+	10+
	No of additional policy makers engaged within the same region(s) – different DGs, units, etc.	60	Lombardy: 80 Catalonia: 60 Brussels: 20 Total: 150

The data show that the majority of the above targets were met and, in some cases, highly surpassed, such as the website visits, the Twitter followers, participation in events and engagement of policymakers in the same region(s).

While Twitter account achieved higher numbers than planned, the LinkedIn group did not manage to generate as much interest as we expected. As explained in the Social media section -

LinkedIn, this can be due to a number of reasons:

- 1/ General online fatigue caused by the Covid-19 pandemic and switch to online activities on all fronts.
- 2/ The fact that each project has existing social media channels to moderate and maintain and there is no space/need to feed such a closed group.

The KPI for the citizen outreach is slightly lower for the COVID impact and the revision of the initial plans in all the 3 regions.

Within the KPI on policymakers reach, the consortium suggested, during the implementation of the project, to add and look at a number of additional policy makers reached within the same region(s) but from different units and directorates-general, to evaluate a wider institutional transformative change within the three regions. The figures on policy makers reach (Table 8) show that all regions managed to engage colleagues, to further raise

awareness about territorial RRI and participatory activities, to build new actions and to further the dissemination of the results after the implementation of the project.

Exploitation

The dissemination endeavours in the last part of the project resulted in a broader awareness of the TRANSFORM activities and approaches beyond the actors and regional authorities involved in TRANSFORM. In particular, the final local events acted as a tremendous multiplier tool to reach further local R&I stakeholders, sometimes also beyond the borders of the engaged territory.

That was the case of the Lombardy cluster, which got the interest of other Italian regions, also for the previous contacts and mutual participation in public events throughout the duration of the project. In particular, ART-ER¹, a partner in the sister project TeRRitoria and a participant in the Lombardy final local event, recruited Fondazione Bassetti for a training programme on public deliberation, based on the TRANSFORM experience in Lombardy, for regional R&I policymaking to be addressed to both ART-ER managers and Emilia-Romagna Region public officials. The training programme started in December 2022 and will continue until the first months of 2023.

The two closing events (the local final event on 10 November, and the Unsold food pilot final workshop on 4 October 2022) also made it possible for the Brussels cluster to strengthen the impact and uptake of its activities beyond the regional partner involved (Innoviris). The Unsold food pilot has been of particular interest for the [4 Wings Foundation](#), a large Belgian foundation dedicated to supporting social innovation fighting poverty. The Foundation funds several initiatives (both entrepreneurial and non-for-profit, mostly citizen-led) dealing with food aid, and making use of unsold food. The Foundation has expressed interest in supporting further steps in the multi-stakeholder engagement process around Unsold food, aiming at both the co-development of shared solutions, and the identification of policy recommendations for regional public agencies (which are encountering major issues and lack of know-how in addressing the topic). In terms of overall impact of the multi-stakeholder approach methodology, the Brussels cluster leader has officially been selected by the regional public agency [Citydev.brussels](#) to be in charge of the preparation of a FEDER proposal on the topic of food logistical support in the region, by making use of the

¹ ART-ER Attractiveness Research Territory is the Emilia-Romagna Joint Stock Consortium born with the purpose of fostering the region's sustainable growth by developing innovation and knowledge, attractiveness and internationalisation of the territory

methodology both in the proposal preparation phase and during its implementation. In both cases, the added value of an RRI approach that leads to a deep understanding of local ecosystem, as well as the identification of shared solutions, by involving citizens and other local actors, has led to long-term impacts and a wider uptake of the methodological approach in the region.

Annex I: Site Map

1. Home – opening banner, general info, clusters, news, partners
2. About
 - About TRANSFORM
 - Partners
 - Advisory Board
3. RRI and S3
4. Citizen Engagement
5. Clusters
 - Brussels-Capital
 - Lombardy
 - Catalonia
6. Shared learning
7. Resources
 - Deliverables
 - Publications
 - Photo gallery
 - Video
8. News (news and updates on project activities, press releases, events, etc.)
9. Final Conference
 - Home page
 - Agenda
 - Call for posters
 - Practical information

www.transform-project.eu

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